

Report on the determinants of innovation uptake and dissemination, impact on farmers' well-being, and recommendations for innovation dissemination

D5.22

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Main author(s):	Piras, S. (JHI); Martínez Sánchez, G. (JHI); Ibn Dahou Idrissi, A. (ENAM); Mokhtari, N. (ENAM); Nchimbi-Msolla, S. (SUA); Kisakye, J. (MAK); Cassius, A. (NARO); Setti, M. (UNIBO)		
Contributor(s):	Kuhfuss, L. (JHI); Scarr, C. (JHI); Mulazzani, L. (UNIBO); Mishili, F. (SUA); Ndetto E. (SUA); Mugisha, J. (MAK); Williams, I. (JHI)		
Reviewed by:	JHI, ENAM, MAK, NARO, SUA		
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Short Description
<p>This document presents the results of the Randomised Controlled Trials (RCTs) implemented in the framework of T5.9 of FoodLAND in the Food Hubs of Meknes (Morocco), Mvomero (Tanzania), and Kajjansi-Masaka (Uganda), deriving implications and recommendations for innovation dissemination. The FoodLAND RCTs had two interrelated goals: (1) assess the impact of different dissemination strategies (information-centred or financial incentives) on innovation uptake by smallholder farmers, and (2) assess the impact of the innovations on farm performance and household wellbeing. Therefore, the report is constituted of two main parts: the analysis of adoption rates at different points along the process; the assessment of whether the innovations made a difference for adopters in terms of farm performance and household wellbeing (using a difference-in-differences approach). This is followed by concise policy recommendations.</p>

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1. Introduction

1.1. Rationale and goals of T5.9

FoodLAND's **Task 5.9** "Innovation validation across the network" had two closely related **goals**:

- 1) Assess the **impact of different dissemination strategies**, based either on information provision or financial incentivisation, on the **adoption** of selected FoodLAND innovations, and
- 2) Assess the **impact of these innovations**, if adopted and used, on various indicators of **farm performance and household wellbeing**.

To achieve the above goals, we implemented **randomised controlled trials** (RCT) in three Food Hubs in Morocco, Tanzania, and Uganda. In each Food Hub, we focused on a specific innovation being developed by the Local FoodLAND partners: in Morocco, a **phone application** for precision irrigation and fertigation and precision protection against the late blight of potatoes; in Tanzania, two **new bean varieties** (called NUA-600 and Mashamba PYT-4) richer in zinc and iron, and with shorter cooking time; in Uganda, the **integration between fish and vegetable farming** by means of pipes that allow the use of aquaculture water for irrigation. The RCTs were conducted between May 2023 (initial survey) and early January 2025 (final survey), with variations depending on the country and on specific local conditions related to the farming season (or aquaculture cycle).

1.2. Rationale and structure of the report

This deliverable, "*D5.22 Report on the determinants of innovation uptake and dissemination, impact on farmers' wellbeing, and recommendations for innovation dissemination*," presents the results of the above activities, and draws recommendations for the dissemination of the FoodLAND innovations. The results derive from the analysis of the RCT datasets, presented within the report "*D5.21: Datasets of randomised controlled trials of farm innovations implemented in Morocco, Tanzania, and Uganda*," and also available in Zenodo.¹

The overall T5.9 activity can be understood as running **two experiments** in each country: the first one focusing on adoption, with three treatment groups (as Treatment 0 is omitted); and the second one focusing on impact for farm performance and wellbeing, with two treatment groups (Treatment 0, as a baseline, vs all the adopters in Treatments 1 to 3, pulled together). For rigorosity, these two sets of experiments were pre-registered online at the Wharton Credibility Lab of the University of Pennsylvania (<https://aspredicted.org/>), and can be accessed at the following links:

- 1) **Morocco**: <https://aspredicted.org/s2gb-qd4c.pdf> for the assessment of adoption behaviours, and <https://aspredicted.org/kjwn-d7x5.pdf> for the analysis of impact;
- 2) **Tanzania**: <https://aspredicted.org/332z-qhmv.pdf> for the assessment of adoption behaviours, and <https://aspredicted.org/r4rv-p5nm.pdf> for the analysis of impact;
- 3) **Uganda**: <https://aspredicted.org/32vb-ntz5.pdf> for the assessment of adoption behaviour, and <https://aspredicted.org/dc49-cbbk.pdf> for the analysis of impact.

In **Morocco**, the baseline survey and training sessions took place between July and August 2023, while the final survey was run in August 2024. This workplan left an entire farming season between the two surveys for farmers to use the phone application and thus assess the impact. In **Tanzania**, the baseline survey took place in March 2024, and the final survey in December 2024. This short implementation period is due to serious constraints in terms of bean multiplication, as SUA needed

¹ Piras, S., Martínez Sánchez, G., Kuhfuss, L., Scarr, C., Ibn Dahou Idrissi, A., Mokhtari, N., Nchimbi-Msolla, S., Kisakye, J., Cassius, A., & Setti, M. (2025). *FoodLAND - Datasets of randomised controlled trials of farm innovations implemented in Morocco, Tanzania, and Uganda* (V1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14714967>.

to generate enough seeds of the two bean varieties to be able to provide them to all the participant farmers. Nevertheless, given the rain pattern in Mvomero, the implementation window still covered two growing seasons. Finally, in **Uganda** a first round of the baseline survey and training was run in May-June 2023. However, the number of participants was not deemed sufficient to draw meaningful conclusions; therefore, while the deadline for submitting the business plan was retained for this first group, the installation of the system was delayed, and another round of survey and training sessions was implemented in April 2024. In turn, the final survey was administered to both groups in the same period (December 2024-January 2025). This implementation window was still enough to cover a full fish production cycle and two vegetable growing seasons.

A detailed overview of the sample size achieved and of the number of adopters by treatment group and country is provided in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Overview of RCT participants and adoption, by phase and country.

Country	Population (innovation)	Treatments	Baseline survey	Final survey	Adoption analysis	Impact analysis
Morocco	Vegetable farmers (phone application for precision irrigation, fertigation, and protection)	T0	101	84	n/a	84 no
		T1	100	91	100 (91)	42 (41) yes
		T2	100	80	100 (80)	53 (48) yes
		T3	100	88	100 (88)	69 (66) yes
		Total	401	343	300 (259)	248 (239)
Tanzania	Bean farmers (new bean varieties NUA-660 and Mashamba PYT-4 rich in zinc and iron)	T0	93	86	n/a	72 no
		T1	112	110	112 (110)	59 yes
		T2	126	120	126 (120)	73 yes
		T3	95	88	95 (88)	63 yes
		Total	426	403	333 (318)	267
Uganda	Fish farmers (integration of fish and vegetable farming though water re-use)	T0	107	105	n/a	104 no
		T1	111	73	111 (73)	14 (12) yes
		T2	91	63	91 (63)	10 (8) yes
		T3	107	79	107 (79)	19 (12) yes
		Total	416	320	309 (215)	147 (136)
TOTAL			1,243	1,066		662 (642)

Notes: The column **“Adoption analysis”** reports the numbers of the baseline survey and, in parentheses, those of the final survey, since different variables were measured at different points. The column **“Impact analysis”** reports the number of respondents to the final survey divided into baseline farmers to which no innovation was proposed who could be retained given the absence of spillover effects (“no”), and adopters (“yes”). The second value for adopters reported in parentheses refers to a stricter definition of adoption.

The analyses of adoption behaviour and of the impact of the innovations on farm performance and household wellbeing presented in the rest of this report follow the procedure described in the pre-registrations above. The calculations were conducted using **R**,² and partly using **Stata 15**.³

The rest of the deliverable is structured as follows. **Section 2** presents the quality of the **randomisation process**, and in particular, how the treatment groups differ in terms of distribution of the farmers between strata (since we implemented “stratified randomisation”). This premise is key to understanding **Section 3**, where we answer to the first research question (objective of T5.9): how different dissemination strategies affected the rate of **innovation adoption**. The following **Section 4** focuses instead on the second research question (objective of T5.9), by assessing the **impact** of the innovations on various indicators of farm performance and household wellbeing. **Section 5** concludes by drawing some **recommendations** for innovation dissemination.

² R Core Team (2022). *R: A language and environment for statistical computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>.

³ StataCorp. 2017. *Stata: Release 15. Statistical Software*. StataCorp LLC, College Station, TX.

2. Stratification outcome

To ensure comparability among the treatment groups in the RCTs, we relied on stratified randomisation. In each country, we created eight strata by cross-tabulating three binary variables which, based on FoodLAND's WP3 surveys, explained a significant share of the variance of other variables. This section provides an overview of the allocation of farmers to the strata in all the countries, i.e., the **quality of the randomisation process**.

In **Morocco**, the randomisation variables were the age of the farmer, the farm size, and the size of the household (a proxy for available family labour). As shown in Figure 1 below, none of these variables differs significantly between the four treatment groups and, consequently, the distribution of the farmers between the strata, illustrated in Figure 2, does not differ significantly either ($\chi^2(21) = 2.626, p = 1.000$). The larger stratum (29.7% of the farmers) is represented by young farmers with small farms, and small households. Given this good randomisation, the results in terms of difference in behaviours between treatment groups are likely to be reliable even without weighting or control variables.

Figure 1: Distribution of the three stratification variables in Morocco

Figure 2: Distribution of the strata in Morocco

In **Tanzania**, the randomisation variables were the commercial orientation of the farm (defined as selling more than 50% of the production in terms of value) as well as the gender and the age of the farmer. Like for Morocco (see Figure 3 below), none of these variables differs significantly between

the four treatment groups and, consequently, the distribution of the farmers between the strata does not differ significantly either ($\chi^2 (21) = 15.478, p = 0.814$), despite looking more unbalanced in Figure 4 below. The larger strata are by far those of market-oriented young, female producers (35.5%) and of market-oriented young, male producers (31.2%), while old subsistence farmers are barely represented, regardless of gender. Hence, we can assume that behaviours and outcomes can be compared between groups with confidence even without using weights or control variables. However, we cannot draw conclusions on whether the sample is representative of the overall farming population.

Figure 3: Distribution of the three stratification variables in Tanzania

Figure 4: Distribution of the strata in Tanzania

Finally, the randomisation variables in **Uganda** were the fact of having received credit or loans for aquaculture in the previous year, the membership in fish farming associations, and the ownership of the pond (as opposed to renting it). Differently from the other two countries, the treatments were allocated to different districts, which limited the scope for balancing the distribution between the strata. As a result, as shown in Figure 5, two out of three variables (association membership, and pond ownership) differ significantly between the treatment groups, and the third one also shows some differentiation. Consequently, the distribution of the farmers between the strata differ

significantly too ($\chi^2(21) = 56.233, p < 0.001$), as suggested by Figure 6 below. The largest stratum is represented by the farmers who own their pond and are members of an association but did not receive any financing (36.1%), followed by those who own their pond and neither received financing nor are association members (27.2%). The latter represents the largest group in T2, and are equally sized with the former in T3. Given this unbalanced distribution, the use of **weights** and control variables is needed to implement a more reliable comparison of the treatment groups.

Figure 5: Distribution of the three stratification variables in Uganda

Figure 6: Distribution of the strata in Uganda

3. Analysis of adoption

For analysing the **uptake of the FoodLAND innovations** and the impact of different treatments on the rate of uptake, we use various regression models tailored to the typology of the outcome (dependent) variable. Since our outcome variables are either binary or ordered categorical, we generally adopt logistic or ordered logistic models. For each outcome variable, we apply four modelling approaches that differ in terms of dependent variables included, and use or non-use of sample weights. Since we used stratified randomisation, but the size of the strata is not always constant across treatment groups, the sample weights are used to ensure that the decisions of the farmers belonging to a specific stratum have the same incidence in each treatment group regardless of the incidence of that stratum in that group. Assuming that the stratum explains a significant share of the variance of other farmer characteristics, this approach would ensure that the outcome variable only depends on the treatment and not on the characteristics of the treatment group. For each country in turn, the weights for each individual farmer i are calculated as $w_{i \in s, t} = \frac{N_s}{N * N_{s, t}}$, where N is the overall sample size, N_s the number of farmers belonging to stratum s in the overall sample, and $N_{s, t}$ the number of farmers belonging to stratum s in treatment t . The weights sum up to 1 for each treatment group. Depending on whether the outcome variable derives from the baseline or final survey, the sample weights are calculated using the distributions from the respective survey. Our four modelling approaches are the following:

1. **Model 1:** Only treatment dummies as explanatory variables, no sample weights.
2. **Model 2:** Only treatment dummies as explanatory variables, with sample weights.
3. **Model 3:** Treatment dummies as well as socio-demographic controls as explanatory variables, no sample weights.
4. **Model 4:** Treatment dummies as well as socio-demographic controls as explanatory variables, with sample weights.

The socio-demographic controls were chosen to account for characteristics that are likely to influence farmers' behaviour but were not already included as stratification variables (or they were, but only as binary). When possible, we tried to include the same controls in all the three countries, deriving their values from the same survey of the dependent variable and, if not present, from the baseline survey. The stratification variables and covariates are listed in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Stratification variables and covariates by country.

Country	Strat. 1	Strat. 2	Strat. 3	Contr. 1	Contr. 2	Contr. 3	Contr. 4	Contr. 5	Contr. 6	Contr. 7
Morocco	Age (young / old)	Household size (small / large)	Land size (small / big)	Age	Gender	Educa-tion	Land size	Adult mem-bers	Association membership	Received loans or credit
Tanzania	Age (young / old)	Gender (male / female)	Commercialisation (>50% / <50%)	Age	n/a	Educa-tion	Land size	Adult mem-bers	Association membership	Received loans or credit
Uganda	Pond owner-ship (yes / no)	Received loans or credit (yes / no)	Association mem-bership (yes / no)	Age	Gender	Educa-tion	Pond size	Adult mem-bers	n/a	n/a

The farmers belonging to the group to which T0 was applied are not included in the analysis of adoption, since no innovation had been presented to the. Therefore, in this part we have three treatment groups. Since T1 represents a baseline dissemination strategy without additional information nor financial incentives, it is excluded from the models to avoid collinearity. Consequently, the coefficients for T2 and T3 tell us if the outcome variable differs significantly from T1 (i.e., the models do not tell us if T2 differs significantly from T3). The treatments applied in each country are recapped in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Treatments pertaining to the dissemination of innovations, by country.

Country	Treatment 1 (innovation, no incentive/info)	Treatment 2	Treatment 3
Morocco	Module A-MO + The app: installation, use, applying the instructions (Module B-MO)	Module A-MO + Module B-MO + Climate change and local impact (Module C-MO) – Climate info	Module A-MO + Module B-MO + Module C-MO + Payment by result with group-level threshold (Module D-MO) – Threshold pay
Tanzania	Module A-TZ + Virtuous practices to grow the new bean lines (Module B-TZ)	Module A-TZ + Module B-TZ + Health benefits of the new bean lines (Module C-TZ) – Health info	Module A-TZ + Module B-TZ + Incentive (+10%) to buy the new bean lines (Module D-TZ) – Discount
Uganda	Module A-UG + Integrated aquaculture system: benefits and installation (Module B-UG)	Module A-UG + Module B-UG + Upfront 15% incentive (Module C-UG) – Upfront pay	Module A-UG + Module B-UG + Upfront 5% incentive plus 25% ex-post incentive by result (Module D-UG) – Result pay

In all the tables in this report, the level of significance of the coefficient is marked as follows: *** indicates significance at 0.01 (1%) level, ** indicates significance at 0.05 (5%) level, and * indicates significance at 0.10 (10%) level.

3.1. Morocco: Climate information and threshold payment

In Morocco, the two dissemination approaches followed for promoting the uptake of the phone application consist respectively in providing detailed information about the local impact of climate change (**T2 – Climate info**) and, additionally to this, a flat-rate individual payment conditional on a collective threshold in terms of use (**T3 – Threshold pay**). The farmers assigned to the latter treatment group were not informed of how their use would be assessed, but only told that they would have to use the app in line with the instructions provided. ENAM defined “minimum acceptable use” as accessing the water needs page of the app 1-2 times per week on average during the farming year, and “optimal use” as accessing the page at least 3 times per week. All the farmers who made at least a “minimum use” of the app received the flat-rate payment if at least 50% of the farmers in their group made an “optimal use of it. We registered **interest in adoption**, actual **adoption**, and **use** of the app at different stages along the process, and the results are discussed here. In particular, for the impact analysis, we consider two alternative definitions of “adopters”: those who made at least a “minimum use” (wider), and those who made an “optimal use” (stricter).

3.1.1. Baseline survey

Figure 7 below shows the distribution of individual sample weights in the baseline survey, while descriptive statistics for the control variables are reported in Table 4. The sample is well balanced in terms of distribution of the farmers between treatment groups, and the differences in the control variables is limited.

Figure 7: Sampling weights for the baseline survey for Morocco

Table 4: Descriptive statistics from the baseline survey for Morocco

Variables		T0 (N=101)	T1 (N=100)	T2 (N=100)	T3 (N=100)	Overall (N=401)
Age	Mean (SD)	48.8 (12.3)	47.2 (15.1)	50.0 (14.7)	47.6 (14.2)	48.4 (14.1)
	Median (IQR)	48.0 (19.0)	49.0 (24.2)	52.0 (19.5)	46.0 (22.0)	49.0 (20.0)
	Range	23.0 - 76.0	18.0 - 77.0	19.0 - 85.0	20.0 - 87.0	18.0 - 87.0
Education	Illiterate	32 (31.7%)	32 (32.0%)	30 (30.0%)	23 (23.0%)	117 (29.2%)
	Literate, no qualification	7 (6.9%)	5 (5.0%)	3 (3.0%)	0 (0.0%)	15 (3.7%)
	Primary	38 (37.6%)	21 (21.0%)	34 (34.0%)	39 (39.0%)	132 (32.9%)
	Secondary	21 (20.8%)	31 (31.0%)	22 (22.0%)	28 (28.0%)	102 (25.4%)
Gender	More than secondary	3 (3.0%)	11 (11.0%)	11 (11.0%)	10 (10.0%)	35 (8.7%)
	Female	9 (8.9%)	8 (8.0%)	9 (9.0%)	3 (3.0%)	29 (7.2%)
	Male	92 (91.1%)	92 (92.0%)	91 (91.0%)	97 (97.0%)	372 (92.8%)
Received loans or credit	No	75 (74.3%)	56 (56.0%)	61 (61.0%)	55 (55.0%)	247 (61.6%)
	Yes	26 (25.7%)	44 (44.0%)	39 (39.0%)	45 (45.0%)	154 (38.4%)
Association membership	No	83 (82.2%)	91 (91.0%)	92 (92.0%)	87 (87.0%)	353 (88.0%)
	Yes	18 (17.8%)	9 (9.0%)	8 (8.0%)	13 (13.0%)	48 (12.0%)

Notes: Due to the small number of farmers who declared to be literate but with no qualifications, this group was merged with those with primary education before proceeding. Equally, for each categorical variable, one level will be omitted for collinearity reasons, thus representing the baseline.

First of all, in the post-training survey the enumerators registered the farmers' **interest in adoption**, namely their interest in installing the app in their phone. The distribution of their responses is provided in Table 5 and illustrated in Figure 8. All the farmers in T3 declared to be interested in installing the app, and almost all immediately, while in T2, 11% stated that they would do so in the future, and in baseline T1, 27% expressed no interest. Therefore, the variable differs significantly between treatments (Table 6), suggesting that the information and, even more, the threshold payment, increased farmers' stated interest. We also observe a strongly significant land size effect, with larger farmers more likely to show interest.

Table 5: Has the farmer expressed the desire to install the application?

Treatment	No	Yes, immediately	Yes, in the future
T1 – Baseline	27	4	69
T2 – Climate info	2	86	11
T3 – Threshold pay	0	99	1

Figure 8: Has the farmer expressed a desire to install the application?

Table 6: Results for desire to install the app

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	0.99(0.18)***	1.02(0.19)***	0.97(0.85)	1.12(0.85)
T2 - Climate info	2.89(0.61)***	2.91(0.63)***	3.00(0.58)***	2.99(0.58)***
T3 - Threshold pay	18.57(881.76)	19.18(1212.78)	19.39(1243.28)	19.01(1043.36)
Age			0.00(0.01)	0.00(0.01)
Education: Primary			0.66(0.5)	0.65(0.5)
Education: Secondary			0.22(0.49)	0.14(0.49)
Education: Above secondary			-0.28(0.64)	-0.30(0.64)
Land size (log)			0.94(0.19)***	0.91(0.19)***
Household size (adults)			-0.14(0.07)**	-0.13(0.07)*
Association membership			0.51(0.68)	0.55(0.68)
Received loans or credit			-0.62(0.37)*	-0.6(0.37)

Notes: While the coefficient for T3 is very large, it is not significant because of the limited variation (only one farmer in that treatment group declared not to be interested in installing the app) that increase the standard deviation a lot.

After the farmers were asked to express their interest in the app, the app was installed in their mobile phones, and the enumerators registered this in the post-training survey. The results in terms of installation are provided in Table 7 and Figure 9 below. Since the distribution is in line with the desire to install, no statistical analysis was conducted.

Table 7: Has the application been installed on the farmer's phone?

Treatment	Before imputation			After imputation	
	No	Yes	Missing	No	Yes
T1 - Baseline	4		96	27	73
T2 - Climate info	19	67	13	2	97
T3 - Threshold pay		99	1	0	100

Notes: The question was only asked to the farmers who expressed a desire to install the app immediately. Therefore, in the following analysis the response for the missing farmers was derived from whether they have used the app, monitored online.

Figure 9: Shares of farmers who have installed the app, based on number of accesses

The farmers who had installed the app were asked what function they were planning to use, i.e., the precision irrigation and fertigation function, or the precision protection one. The results for the **precision irrigation and fertigation** function are shown in Table 8 and Figure 10 below, and analysed in Table 9. They suggest widespread interest in this function, which is also the main one and the one on which we focused the RCT. 91% of the farmers who had installed the app intended to use this function, with no significant differences between the treatment groups.

Table 8: What function of the app do you plan to use? Precision irrigation and fertigation

Treatment	No	Yes
T1 – Baseline	5	68
T2 - Climate info	10	87
T3 - Threshold pay	9	91

Figure 10: Shares of farmers who plan to use the precision irrigation and fertigation function

Table 9: Results of binomial models for those farmers who plan to use the precision irrigation and fertigation function

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	2.61(0.47)***	2.63(0.47)***	2.8(1.12)**	2.75(1.1)**
T2 - Climate info	-0.45(0.57)	-0.45(0.58)	-0.39(0.59)	-0.39(0.60)
T3 - Threshold pay	-0.3(0.58)	-0.42(0.58)	-0.31(0.60)	-0.42(0.60)
Age			0.00(0.02)	0.00(0.02)
Education: Primary			-0.48(0.60)	-0.41(0.59)
Education: Secondary			-0.31(0.73)	-0.18(0.71)
Education: Above secondary			-0.61(0.84)	-0.55(0.82)
Land size (log)			0.15(0.23)	0.15(0.23)
Household size (adults)			-0.06(0.09)	-0.05(0.09)
Association membership			0.94(1.08)	0.97(1.09)
Received loans or credit			0.21(0.46)	0.13(0.46)

In turn, the **precision protection** function was less popular, with 75% of the farmers being interested in using it. The distribution across treatment groups is shown in Table 10 and Figure 11 below, and analysed in Table 11. Differently from what we were expecting, the farmers in T2 and, even more, in T3 declared to be less likely to use the precision protection function of the app compared to the baseline T1, but the difference is only significant for T3. Additionally, we observe significant and negative coefficients for association membership and having received loans or credit, suggesting that these farmers may have other means to protect themselves from potato late blight, e.g., advice from their group of belonging. It must be highlighted that no late blight outbreaks were reported during the period of the RCT; therefore, we do not report any descriptive statistics concerning the questions aimed at assessing the app's impact in this regard, and this specific function might have become less salient. We must also highlight that the farmers were not randomised based on growing potatoes (the target crop of this function); therefore, the counterintuitive difference between treatments might have been driven by a higher prevalence of potato growers in the baseline treatment group.

Table 10: What function of the app do you plan to use? Precision protection

Treatment	No	Yes
T1 – Baseline	11	62
T2 - Climate info	23	74
T3 - Threshold pay	34	66

Figure 11: Shares of farmers who plan to use the precision protection function

Table 11: Results of binomial models for those farmers who plan to use the precision protection function

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	1.73(0.33)***	1.71(0.33)***	0.83(0.79)	0.69(0.79)
T2 - Climate info	-0.56(0.41)	-0.55(0.41)	-0.74(0.44)*	-0.73(0.44)*
T3 - Threshold pay	-1.07(0.39)***	-1.02(0.39)***	-1.1(0.42)***	-1.09(0.42)**
Age			0.01(0.01)	0.02(0.01)
Education: Primary			0.48(0.42)	0.57(0.42)
Education: Secondary			0.02(0.46)	0.10(0.46)
Education: Above secondary			-0.23(0.56)	-0.19(0.56)
Land size (log)			-0.13(0.17)	-0.11(0.17)
Household size (adults)			0.17(0.08)**	0.17(0.08)**
Association membership			-1.09(0.48)**	-1.15(0.48)**
Received loans or credit			-0.55(0.32)*	-0.54(0.32)*

3.1.2. Final survey

The variables discussed below refer to the final survey, i.e., they were gathered at the end of the demonstration period and therefore, they reflect more precisely the real behaviour of the farmers with respect to the innovation. Sample weights were calculated for this survey too, and they are plotted in Figure 12, while Table 12 shows that, despite an attrition of 14.5% between the baseline and the final survey, the characteristics of the farmers in terms of key control variables remained comparable between treatment groups.

Figure 12: Sampling weights for the final survey for Morocco

Table 12: Descriptive statistics from the final survey for Morocco

Variables		T0 (N=84)	T1 (N=91)	T2 (N=80)	T3 (N=88)	Overall (N=343)
Age	Mean (SD)	49.1 (12.9)	49.0 (15.6)	51.0 (15.6)	48.2 (14.3)	49.3 (14.6)
	Median (IQR)	48.0 (20.2)	51.0 (24.0)	53.0 (22.0)	47.0 (22.0)	49.0 (22.0)
	Range	24.0 - 82.0	19.0 - 81.0	20.0 - 86.0	21.0 - 88.0	19.0 - 88.0
Education	Illiterate	24 (28.6%)	32 (35.2%)	22 (27.5%)	18 (20.5%)	96 (28.0%)
	Literate, no qualifications	6 (7.1%)	4 (4.4%)	3 (3.8%)	0 (0.0%)	13 (3.8%)
	Primary	32 (38.1%)	18 (19.8%)	26 (32.5%)	34 (38.6%)	110 (32.1%)
	Secondary	20 (23.8%)	28 (30.8%)	19 (23.8%)	26 (29.5%)	93 (27.1%)
Gender	Above secondary	2 (2.4%)	9 (9.9%)	10 (12.5%)	10 (11.4%)	31 (9.0%)
	Female	7 (8.3%)	7 (7.7%)	7 (8.8%)	3 (3.4%)	24 (7.0%)
Received loans or credit	Male	77 (91.7%)	84 (92.3%)	73 (91.2%)	85 (96.6%)	319 (93.0%)
	No	57 (67.9%)	62 (68.1%)	53 (66.2%)	56 (63.6%)	228 (66.5%)
Association membership	Yes	27 (32.1%)	29 (31.9%)	27 (33.8%)	32 (36.4%)	115 (33.5%)
	No	70 (83.3%)	82 (90.1%)	72 (90.0%)	77 (87.5%)	301 (87.8%)
	Yes	14 (16.7%)	9 (9.9%)	8 (10.0%)	11 (12.5%)	42 (12.2%)

As a first step, as a robustness check, we asked the same question of the baseline survey, i.e., whether the farmer had **installed the app**. The distribution, reported in Table 13 and Figure 13, is very similar to the one obtained after the training, suggesting that the attrition concerned installers and non-installers in similar proportions, at least among T1 farmers.

Table 13: Installation of the app at the end of the training, by treatment

Treatment	No	Yes	Missing
T1 - Baseline	27	63	1
T2 - Climate info	1	79	0
T3 - Threshold pay	0	88	0

Figure 13: Shares of farmers who installed the app, based on the final survey

In order to control for spillover effects between treatment groups, but also to assess the positive spillovers of FoodLAND research beyond the farmers involved, we asked all the participants if they had **discussed the app** with other farmers. The results are reported in Table 14 and Figure 14 below, and analysed statistically in Table 15. Overall, more than half of the farmers (54.5%) spoke about the app with other farmers not involved in the RCT and interestingly, the percentage differs significantly between treatment groups, increasing between 36% in the baseline T1 group, to 59% in T2, to 69% in T3. The treatment is the only explanatory variable that yields significant coefficients, suggesting that the information about climate change and, even more, the incentive, had probably increased the salience of the innovation and the credibility of the institution who had introduced it, resulting in wider impact than among the FoodLAND farmers.

Table 14: Frequency table of farmers that have discussed the app with other farmers

Treatment	No	Yes
T1 - Baseline	58	33
T2 - Climate info	33	47
T3 - Threshold pay	27	61

Figure 14: Shares of farmers who discussed the app with other farmers

Table 15: Logistic model for the farmers who have discussed the app with other farmers

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-0.56(0.22)**	-0.47(0.22)**	-0.34(0.77)	0(0.75)
T2 - Climate info	0.92(0.32)***	0.82(0.31)***	0.95(0.33)***	0.87(0.32)***
T3 - Threshold pay	1.38(0.32)***	1.34(0.33)***	1.43(0.33)***	1.41(0.34)***
Age			0.00(0.01)	0.00(0.01)
Gender: Male			-0.01(0.55)	-0.20(0.53)
Education: Primary			-0.21(0.35)	-0.26(0.35)
Education: Secondary			0.02(0.39)	-0.08(0.39)
Education: Above secondary			0.44(0.51)	0.38(0.51)
Received loans or credit			-0.27(0.29)	-0.26(0.29)
Household size (adults)			-0.01(0.05)	0.02(0.05)

In the final survey, we assessed again whether the farmers had used each of the function of the app, thus verifying whether their intentions match their actual behaviour. The results for the **precision irrigation and fertigation function** are reported in Table 16 and Figure 15 below, and analysed statistically in Table 17. We do not report the results for the precision protection function because most farmers declared that they had used it, i.e., they had the function active in the app, but we know that this was not needed because no outbreaks of potato late blight were recorded during the demonstration year. Interestingly, while the distribution of intention did not differ significantly by treatment, here we observe a significant difference between the baseline group T1, where 70% of the farmers did not use the function, and the other two groups, where virtually everyone declared to have used it. Again, the treatment dummies are the only variables yielding statistically significant coefficients.

Table 16: Frequency table of farmers that use the function of irrigation and fertigation

Treatment	No	Yes
T1 - Baseline	27	64
T2 - Climate info	1	79
T3 - Threshold pay	1	87

Figure 15: Shares of farmers that used the function of irrigation and fertigation

Table 17: Results of farmers that used the function of irrigation and fertigation

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	0.86(0.23)***	0.98(0.24)***	0.78(1.19)	1.02(1.26)
T2 - Climate info	3.51(1.04)***	3.65(1.14)***	3.56(1.04)***	3.68(1.13)***
T3 - Threshold pay	3.60(1.04)***	3.59(1.10)***	3.60(1.04)***	3.61(1.10)***
Age			0.00(0.02)	0.00(0.02)
Gender: Male			0.61(0.78)	0.48(0.84)
Education: Primary			-0.15(0.60)	-0.12(0.64)
Education: Secondary			-0.21(0.61)	-0.27(0.64)
Education: Above secondary			-0.45(0.81)	-0.41(0.85)
Received loans or credit			-0.17(0.48)	-0.05(0.50)
Household size (adults)			-0.07(0.08)	-0.04(0.09)

Since we are interested in the long-term sustainability of the FoodLAND project’s benefits, we asked farmers if they intended to keep **using the innovation in the future**. Obviously, we can only register intentions in this regard, not actual use, and indeed the distribution of the responses is skewed towards positive responses, with no one stating that they were “unlikely” to keep using the app. In Table 18 and Figure 16 below, we report the distribution of the farmers’ responses as ordered categorical, then we turn the variable into a dummy (“likely” vs “quite likely” or less) and estimate a model, reported in Table 19. Noteworthy, the farmers who were provided information in T2 or were given the opportunity to receive an incentive in T3 are significantly more likely to keep using the app in the future, at least according to their declarations. This suggests that information about the local impact of climate change and incentives can potentially generate a long-term impact. Additionally, secondary education is associated with higher likelihood to keep using the app.

Table 18: Frequency table of likelihood to keep using the app in the future

Treatment	Neither	Quite likely	Likely
T1 – Baseline	7	44	12
T2 - Climate info	7	44	28
T3 - Threshold pay	3	43	42

Figure 16: Shares of farmers who intend to keep using the app in the future

Table 19: Results of binomial models for those farmers who are likely to keep using the app

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-1.45(0.32)***	-1.46(0.33)***	-0.82(0.87)	-1.10(0.84)
T2 - Climate info	0.85(0.40)**	0.83(0.40)**	0.9(0.42)**	0.89(0.42)**
T3 - Threshold pay	1.36(0.39)***	1.38(0.40)***	1.43(0.41)***	1.46(0.42)***
Age			0.00(0.01)	0.00(0.01)
Gender: Male			-0.86(0.60)	-0.84(0.55)
Education: Primary			0.02(0.40)	0.17(0.40)
Education: Secondary			0.81(0.44)*	1.01(0.45)**
Education: Above secondary			0.57(0.54)	0.69(0.55)
Received loans or credit			-0.12(0.32)	-0.14(0.32)
Household size (adults)			-0.06(0.07)	-0.06(0.06)

We replicate the above analysis focusing on the two functions of the app separately. Table 20 and Figure 17 below report the results for the **precision irrigation and fertigation** function, which are very similar to those for the app overall, only more skewed towards positive responses. After the categorical variable is turned into a dummy using the same approach as above (Table 21), we observe a significant positive coefficient for T3, and a positive but no-significant one for T2.

Table 20: Frequency table of farmers that are likely to use the precision irrigation and fertigation function in the future

Treatment	Neither	Quite likely	Very likely
T1 – Baseline	8	38	17
T2 - Climate info	4	45	30
T3 - Threshold pay	4	43	41

Figure 17: Shares of farmers by likelihood of keeping using the precision irrigation and fertigation function in the future

Table 21: Results of a binomial models for those farmers that use the function of protection and fertigation in the future

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-1(0.29)***	-1.03(0.29)***	-0.83(0.85)	-0.93(0.80)
T2 - Climate info	0.5(0.37)	0.51(0.37)	0.57(0.38)	0.56(0.38)
T3 - Threshold pay	0.86(0.36)**	0.87(0.37)**	0.92(0.37)**	0.93(0.38)**
Age			0.00(0.01)	0.00(0.01)
Gender: Male			0.03(0.61)	-0.12(0.55)
Education: Primary			-0.37(0.38)	-0.15(0.38)
Education: Secondary			0.27(0.41)	0.45(0.42)
Education: Above secondary			0.10(0.52)	0.30(0.52)
Received loans or credit			-0.19(0.31)	-0.22(0.31)
Household size (adults)			-0.01(0.06)	-0.01(0.06)

The results for the **precision protection** function confirm what already observed based on the responses in the initial survey, that there is no significant difference between treatment groups, or at least no difference in the expected direction. As reported in Table 22 and Figure 18 below, only 48.7% of the farmers overall are “quite likely” or “likely” to keep using this app function in the future, with only the gender (male) being a marginally significant and positive predictor (Table 23). While this response is likely to be affected by the number of farmers who grow potatoes in each group and by the absence of late blight outbreaks in the period of the RCT, the distribution of the responses along the whole scale can be seen as a sign of reliability of the farmers’ responses to other questions too, as they were not affected by a social desirability bias.

Table 22: Frequency table of farmers that are likely to use the precision protection function in the future

Treatment	Unsure	Very unlikely	Neither	Quite likely	Very likely
T1 - Baseline	14	12	5	14	18
T2 - Climate info	7	30	6	11	25
T3 - Threshold pay	16	22	6	14	30

Figure 18: Shares of farmers by likelihood of keeping using the precision protection function in the future

Table 23: Results of binomial models for those farmers who are likely to use the precision protection function in the future

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-0.92(0.28)***	-0.92(0.29)***	-0.94(1.01)	-1.33(0.97)
T2 - Climate info	0.15(0.37)	0.16(0.37)	0.26(0.39)	0.28(0.39)
T3 - Threshold pay	0.26(0.36)	0.19(0.37)	0.34(0.38)	0.31(0.39)
Age			-0.02(0.01)*	-0.02(0.01)
Gender: Male			1.32(0.82)	1.53(0.79)*
Education: Primary			-0.65(0.39)*	-0.59(0.39)
Education: Secondary			-0.51(0.43)	-0.42(0.44)
Education: Above secondary			-0.40(0.54)	-0.19(0.53)
Received loans or credit			-0.41(0.33)	-0.41(0.33)
Household size (adults)			0.06(0.06)	0.05(0.06)

As a last step, we analyse the **frequency of using the application** based on the average monthly accesses to the water needs page during the demonstration period (July 2023 to July 2024). This variable can be considered the most reliable proxy of use of the app, and indeed we will use it, and in particular the definitions of “minimum acceptable use” and “optimal use” developed by ENAM, to identify adopters for the analysis of impact. Across the entire sample, the **rate of adoption** defined as such is **54.7%** (164 farmers) if considering both “minimal” and “optimal” users, and **51.7%** (155 farmers) if considering “optimal” users only. The distribution is clearly bimodal (Figure 19 below), with a peak on non-users whose monthly accesses is only slightly larger than zero, and a second, larger peak of users whose average number of monthly accesses ranges between 20 and 45. The pattern of the distribution is similar across the three treatment groups, as shown in Figure 20, with slight differences between the peaks: the right side one becomes relatively larger in T3.

To model this variable, we transformed it into an ordered categorical one using cluster analysis. The cluster dendrogram is reported in Figure 21, the incidence and use behaviour in the five clusters identified (that we name from “never” to “always”) is reported in Table 24, and the distribution of the farmers between clusters across treatment groups is shown in Figure 22. It must be noted that we modify the first two clusters to distinguish between no use at all (“Never”) and at least some use, although negligible (“Rarely”). A Pearson’s χ -squared test suggests that the frequency of use differs significantly between the treatment groups; however, the pattern is not trivial, and requires a more in-depth analysis.

Figure 19: Distribution of the average number of monthly accesses to the water needs page

Figure 20: Distribution of the average number of monthly accesses to the water needs page of the app, by treatment group

Figure 21: Cluster dendrogram for the average number of monthly accesses to the water needs page of the app

Table 24: Size and range of the clusters in terms of use of the app (number of accesses)

Cluster	Average	Minimum	Median	Maximum	Farmers (n)
Never	0.79	0.00	0.77	1.00	30
Rarely	3.47	1.08	2.27	9.69	62
Sometimes	26.61	21.85	27.38	29.00	43
Often	32.05	29.31	31.81	34.77	94
Always	37.11	35.00	36.85	43.77	41

Notes: Pearson's χ -squared test with simulated p -value (based on 2,000 bootstrap replicates) of the difference of distribution across the three treatment groups: χ -squared = 16.473, d.f. = NA, p -value = 0.037 **.

Figure 22: Distribution of the farmers between the clusters in terms of use, by treatment

First, we estimate ordinal models with all the five levels separately. The model estimates are reported in Table 25 below, and suggest that there is no significant difference in the frequency of app use between the treatment groups. Additionally, no one of the control variables yields a significant coefficient (the first four lines in the table report the level of significance of the cutoff points between levels instead).

Table 25: Results of an ordinal models for the use of app

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Never Rarely	-1.87(0.26)***	-1.86(2.62)	-1.50(0.68)**	-1.50(6.7)
Rarely Sometimes	-0.44(0.22)**	-0.43(2.22)	-0.06(0.67)	-0.05(6.58)
Sometimes Often	0.22(0.22)	0.22(2.19)	0.61(0.67)	0.60(6.57)
Often Always	1.94(0.25)***	1.95(2.53)	2.35(0.68)***	2.34(6.71)
T2 - Climate info	0.26(0.29)	0.27(2.85)	0.23(0.29)	0.25(2.88)
T3 - Threshold pay	0.33(0.27)	0.34(2.73)	0.30(0.28)	0.33(2.75)
Age			0.00(0.01)	0.00(0.09)
Gender: Male			0.52(0.49)	0.52(4.78)
Education: Primary			0.12(0.29)	0.11(2.88)
Education: Secondary			0.16(0.35)	0.13(3.47)
Education: Above secondary			0.67(0.43)	0.61(4.29)
Land size (log)			-0.19(0.12)	-0.18(1.19)
Household size (adults)			-0.02(0.05)	-0.01(0.50)
Association membership			0.33(0.41)	0.30(4.09)
Received loans or credit			0.10(0.23)	0.13(2.27)

As a following step, we define a dummy variable that takes value 1 if the farmer had installed the app but “never” used it, and 0 otherwise. The distribution of this variable across treatment groups is shown in Figure 23 below, and the results of binomial models are reported in Table 26. Noteworthy, the share of farmers who did not engage with the app is significantly lower among the T3

group, and lower, but non-significant, in the T2 group, compared to the baseline T1, suggesting that the threshold incentive was successful in pushing farmers to use the innovation. No control variable yields a significant coefficient.

Figure 23: Share of farmers who installed the app but never used it

Table 26: Results of binomial models for those farmers who never used the app

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-1.53(0.31)***	-1.52(0.31)***	-0.67(1.13)	-0.82(1.13)
T2 - Climate info	-0.43(0.44)	-0.45(0.44)	-0.46(0.46)	-0.47(0.46)
T3 - Threshold pay	-1.42(0.55)**	-1.44(0.56)**	-1.36(0.58)**	-1.41(0.58)**
Age			0.00(0.02)	0.00(0.02)
Gender: Male			-0.49(0.74)	-0.44(0.74)
Education: Primary			-0.36(0.52)	-0.32(0.52)
Education: Secondary			-0.15(0.60)	-0.12(0.60)
Education: Above secondary			-0.62(0.88)	-0.53(0.87)
Received loans or credit			-0.68(0.47)	-0.70(0.47)
Household size (adults)			0.00(0.09)	0.00(0.09)

As a further step, we defined a dummy variable that takes value 1 if the farmer has installed the app but had **used it only “rarely” or “never”**, 0 otherwise. The distribution of this variable across treatment groups is shown in Figure 24 below, and the results of binomial models are reported in Table 27. In this case, the coefficient is positive and significant for T2 only, suggesting that the farmers in that group were more likely to have a low level of engagement with the app (but not zero). By considering this and the previous set of models together, we can conclude that the information alone led farmers to engage with the app, but the incentive was more effective in triggering a switch from limited to frequent and thus more appropriate and possibly, effective use. A well-designed mix of information provision and financial incentivisation conditional on a relevant collective outcome could thus represent a promising approach in case of large-scale implementation.

Figure 24: Share of farmers who installed the app but used it rarely or never

Table 27: Results of binomial models for those farmers who used the app “rarely” or less

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-0.99(0.23)***	-0.98(0.23)***	-1.00(0.76)	-0.94(0.74)
T2 - Climate info	0.52(0.31)*	0.52(0.31)*	0.55(0.31)*	0.54(0.31)*
T3 - Threshold pay	0.00(0.32)	-0.02(0.32)	0.01(0.33)	-0.01(0.33)
Age			0.00(0.01)	0.00(0.01)
Gender: Male			0.00(0.53)	-0.03(0.52)
Education: Primary			-0.07(0.33)	-0.07(0.33)
Education: Secondary			-0.03(0.39)	-0.05(0.39)
Education: Above secondary			-0.81(0.54)	-0.73(0.53)
Received loans or credit			0.07(0.27)	0.04(0.27)
Household size (adults)			0.03(0.05)	0.03(0.05)

To conclude the analysis of adoption in Morocco, it is worth making some considerations on the **cost of incentivisation**. Among the 100 farmers who were assigned to the T3 group, 74 (of which one “minimal” user and 73 “optimal” users) were awarded the flat-rate payment of EUR 50, for a total cost of **EUR 3,700**. There was no actual monitoring of whether the recommendations provided by the app were followed by the farmers, nor of the results achieved on-farm (e.g., water savings): only the number of accesses to the water needs page were monitored. Hence, the other costs (mostly related to running the training) are likely to be similar between the treatment groups. While a cost-efficiency analysis is out of the scope of this report, and would require longer-term demonstration, some readers could anyway retain that the higher level of engagement with the app in T3 and the spillover effects such as discussing with other farmers justify the additional cost.

3.2. Tanzania: Healthiness information and small discount

In Tanzania, the uptake of the new bean varieties (NUA-600 and Mashamba PYT-4) was promoted using two approaches. First, through the provision of detailed information about the health benefits of iron and zinc (the nutrients of which the new varieties are rich), including overview of the illnesses that these nutrients can help prevent (**T2 – Health info**), and a small discount for a limited period of time, i.e., the possibility of purchasing 10% more seeds compared to the quantity of the standard varieties which could be purchased for the same price, if the decision was made immediately after the training (**T3 – Discount**). Despite the efforts of the SUA team in multiplying the seed, the quantity of Mashamba PYT-4 was not enough for all the farmers assigned to T1, T2 and T3. Thus, to avoid censoring the decision variable, they were first asked to state their **interest in purchasing** the seeds of one or both varieties, which was registered, and to provide the means of **payment** (cash, other beans, or maize). Only afterwards, some farmers, randomly extracted, were provided the seeds of Mashamba PYT-4, while the others were informed that this variety was not available.

Given the need to make a decision immediately to avoid spill-over effects, for Tanzania we do not measure interest in adoption proper, but our interest variable represents the purchasing decision. However, this decision did not necessarily result in **growing** and/or **consuming** the new varieties, two aspects that were thus assessed through the final survey. Moreover, the farmers had to **recall** their practices during the last growing seasons, which could lead to assessment **errors**, especially given the need to distinguish the two varieties despite their recent introduction in the area. For this reason, in the final survey, the farmers were **asked again** if they had purchased NUA-600 and/or Mashamba PYT-4 after the training in spring, and were shown the seeds. In the rest of the section, we present their responses in both occurrences.

3.2.1. Baseline survey

As a starting point, Figure 25 below shows the distribution of individual sample weights in the initial survey, while descriptive statistics for the control variables are reported in Table 28. Compared to other countries, the sample is particularly well balanced, with the partial exception of age, which increases as we move from T0 to T3, and the education level, slightly lower in T2. Similarly to what done elsewhere, we will present statistical models with and without controls and sample weights.

Figure 25: Sampling weights for the baseline survey for Tanzania

After the training sessions, the farmers in the treatment groups T1, T2, and T3 were provided with an opportunity to purchase the new bean varieties or exchange them with maize or with the seeds of standard varieties grown in their village, if they had already purchased them. To make sure that the decision variable was not censored, all the participants had been asked to bring cash, beans, or maize. The standard variety grown in the village was always available to purchase alongside the new varieties, being the only one available to the T0 group (not included here). There was no limit to the number of varieties that each farm could purchase (except Mashamba PYT-4, but this was communicated only after the decision). Table 29 and Figure 26 below report the distribution of the farmers depending on **whether they wanted to purchase** the new varieties. The values are very similar for the two varieties: 69% of the farmers intended to purchase either of them, with only one farmer being interested in Mashamba PYT-4, not in NUA-660. This similarity was expected, since the two varieties had similar characteristics in terms of nutrient content and cooking time, and were presented jointly. The slight difference may be due to the appearance of the seeds (e.g., the colour), which could affect saleability. Although the farmers assigned to T3 bought the two varieties in larger proportions, the models presented in Table 30 suggest that this difference of about 10% is not statistically significant (the model for Mashamba PYT-4 do not differ significantly from those presented; therefore, they are not reported). Noteworthy, older farmers were significantly less likely to purchase the new varieties, and those with primary or lower education, more likely.

Table 28: Descriptive statistics from the baseline survey for Tanzania

Variables		T0 (N=93)	T1 (N=112)	T2 (N=126)	T3 (N=95)	Overall (N=426)
Age	Mean (SD)	38.2 (14.8)	38.7 (16.2)	40.9 (14.2)	42.6 (14.9)	40.1 (15.1)
	Median (IQR)	36.0 (18.0)	35.0 (23.0)	37.0 (21.8)	40.0 (20.5)	37.0 (22.0)
	Range	18.0 - 77.0	18.0 - 85.0	18.0 - 76.0	20.0 - 89.0	18.0 - 89.0
Education	Illiterate	18 (19.4%)	27 (24.1%)	22 (17.5%)	22 (23.2%)	89 (20.9%)
	Literate with no qualifications	3 (3.2%)	1 (0.9%)	2 (1.6%)	1 (1.1%)	7 (1.6%)
	Primary	57 (61.3%)	69 (61.6%)	93 (73.8%)	61 (64.2%)	280 (65.7%)
	Secondary	13 (14.0%)	13 (11.6%)	8 (6.3%)	10 (10.5%)	44 (10.3%)
	More than secondary	2 (2.2%)	2 (1.8%)	1 (0.8%)	1 (1.1%)	6 (1.4%)
Land size	Mean (SD)	1.7 (1.5)	1.8 (1.8)	2.0 (3.1)	1.7 (1.4)	1.8 (2.1)
	Median (IQR)	1.2 (1.2)	1.2 (1.2)	1.2 (1.2)	1.2 (1.2)	1.2 (1.2)
	Range	0.3 - 10.1	0.3 - 11.9	0.4 - 28.3	0.2 - 8.1	0.2 - 28.3
Household size (adults)	Mean (SD)	2.9 (1.5)	2.8 (1.2)	2.9 (1.4)	2.9 (1.7)	2.8 (1.4)
	Median (IQR)	3.0 (2.0)	2.0 (1.0)	2.0 (1.8)	3.0 (1.0)	2.0 (1.0)
	Range	1.0 - 8.0	1.0 - 7.0	1.0 - 7.0	1.0 - 13.0	1.0 - 13.0
Association membership	No	90 (96.8%)	107 (95.5%)	122 (96.8%)	90 (94.7%)	409 (96.0%)
	Yes	3 (3.2%)	5 (4.5%)	4 (3.2%)	5 (5.3%)	17 (4.0%)
Received loans or credit	No	74 (79.6%)	81 (72.3%)	100 (79.4%)	68 (71.6%)	323 (75.8%)
	Yes	19 (20.4%)	31 (27.7%)	26 (20.6%)	27 (28.4%)	103 (24.2%)

Notes: Due to the small number of farmers who declared to be literate but with no qualifications, or to have more than secondary education, the levels of the education variable were reduced to two before proceeding. Equally, for each categorical variable, one level will be omitted for collinearity reasons, thus representing the baseline.

Table 29: Number of farmers who purchased the new varieties, by treatment

Treatment	No	Yes
T1 - Baseline	37	75
T2 - Health info	43 / 42	83 / 84
T3 - Discount	23	72

Notes: The figure after "/" refers to Mashamba PYT-4. If only a value is provided, it means that it does not differ depending on the variety.

Figure 26: Share of farmers who purchased the new variety NUA-660, by treatment

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Table 30: Binomial models for the share of farmers who purchased the new variety NUA-660

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	0.71(0.20)***	0.7(0.20)***	1.04(0.52)**	0.95(0.52)*
T2 - Health info	-0.05(0.28)	-0.07(0.29)	-0.03(0.29)	-0.07(0.30)
T3 - Discount	0.43(0.31)	0.49(0.30)	0.52(0.33)	0.51(0.32)
Age			-0.02(0.01)***	-0.02(0.01)**
Education: Primary or lower			0.58(0.30)*	0.63(0.30)**
Education: Secondary or higher			0.18(0.49)	0.38(0.48)
Land size (log)			0.25(0.19)	0.23(0.19)
Household size (adults)			0.02(0.10)	-0.01(0.09)
Received loans or credit			0.40(0.31)	0.50(0.31)
Association membership			1.09(0.81)	1.08(0.81)

After purchasing the bean varieties or having been assigned Mashamba PYT-4, the farmers were asked whether they had changed their plans in terms of **growing beans during the next season**, compared to their previous declaration in the baseline survey. Indeed, when answering the baseline survey, they were not aware of the existence of the new varieties; on the other hand, they may have bought the new varieties for other reasons, like consuming or donating them. The numbers for NUA-660 are reported in Table 31, while the usual set of model is provided in Table 32. These numbers are quite similar to those referring to purchasing the beans, with the main exception that T3 (the discount) yields a significant and positive coefficient. The farmer's age remains a negative and significant predictor, while a primary or lower level of education is significant and positive.

Table 31: Share of farmers who intended to grow the new variety NUA-660 (Mashamba PYT-4 would be equivalent), by treatment

Treatment	Yes	No
T1 - Baseline	74	38
T2 - Health info	83	43
T3 - Discount	72	23

Notes: The farmers who did not show up at the final survey take value 0 ("no").

Table 32: Binomial models for those farmers intended to grow the new variety NUA-660 (Mashamba PYT-4 would be equivalent) after the training

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	0.67(0.2)***	0.65(0.2)***	0.83(0.53)	0.75(0.53)
T2 - Health info	-0.01(0.28)	-0.02(0.28)	0.01(0.29)	-0.02(0.30)
T3 - Discount	0.47(0.31)	0.53(0.30)*	0.57(0.33)*	0.56(0.32)*
Age			-0.03(0.01)***	-0.02(0.01)***
Education: Primary or lower			0.65(0.30)**	0.72(0.30)**
Education: Secondary or higher			0.28(0.49)	0.48(0.49)
Land size (log)			0.19(0.19)	0.19(0.19)
Household size (adults)			0.08(0.10)	0.05(0.10)
Received loans or credit			0.51(0.31)	0.60(0.31)*
Association membership			1.08(0.82)	1.08(0.82)

3.2.2. Final survey

The variables below were gathered at the end of the training, while those presented in this section derive from the final survey, and thus reflect more precisely the farmers' behaviour with respect to the new bean varieties. Sample weights were calculated for this survey too, and their distribution is plotted in Figure 27, while Table 33 shows that the characteristics of the farmers in terms of the control variables do not differ significantly between treatment groups, again with the partial exception of age and education. Indeed, the level of attrition in Tanzania was limited, with only 5.9% of

the respondents lost between the baseline and the final surveys (two farmers only took part in the final survey and were retained to increase impact, but are not accounted for here).

Figure 27: Sampling weights for the final survey for Tanzania

Table 33: Descriptive statistics from the final survey for Tanzania

Variables		T0 (N=86)	T1 (N=107)	T2 (N=119)	T3 (N=89)	Overall (N=401)
Age	Mean (SD)	38.9 (14.9)	38.7 (16.3)	41.9 (14.0)	42.0 (13.9)	40.4 (14.8)
	Median (IQR)	36.0 (19.2)	35.0 (22.5)	38.0 (22.0)	40.0 (21.0)	37.0 (21.0)
	Range	18.0 - 77.0	18.0 - 85.0	19.0 - 76.0	20.0 - 89.0	18.0 - 89.0
Education	Illiterate	14 (16.3%)	26 (24.3%)	20 (16.8%)	19 (21.3%)	79 (19.7%)
	Literate with no qualifications	3 (3.5%)	1 (0.9%)	2 (1.7%)	1 (1.1%)	7 (1.7%)
	Primary	54 (62.8%)	65 (60.7%)	87 (73.1%)	58 (65.2%)	264 (65.8%)
	Secondary	13 (15.1%)	13 (12.1%)	8 (6.7%)	10 (11.2%)	44 (11.0%)
Association membership	More than secondary	2 (2.3%)	2 (1.9%)	2 (1.7%)	1 (1.1%)	7 (1.7%)
	No	83 (96.5%)	102 (95.3%)	115 (96.6%)	84 (94.4%)	384 (95.8%)
Received loans or credit	Yes	3 (3.5%)	5 (4.7%)	4 (3.4%)	5 (5.6%)	17 (4.2%)
	No	65 (75.6%)	83 (77.6%)	87 (73.1%)	70 (78.7%)	305 (76.1%)
Household size (adults)	Yes	21 (24.4%)	24 (22.4%)	32 (26.9%)	19 (21.3%)	96 (23.9%)
	Mean (SD)	2.9 (1.5)	2.8 (1.2)	2.8 (1.4)	2.9 (1.7)	2.8 (1.4)
	Median (IQR)	2.0 (2.0)	2.0 (1.0)	2.0 (1.5)	3.0 (1.0)	2.0 (1.0)
Land size	Range	1.0 - 8.0	1.0 - 7.0	1.0 - 7.0	1.0 - 13.0	1.0 - 13.0
	Mean (SD)	1.7 (1.5)	1.8 (1.8)	2.0 (3.2)	1.7 (1.4)	1.8 (2.2)
	Median (IQR)	1.2 (1.2)	1.2 (1.2)	1.2 (1.2)	1.2 (1.2)	1.2 (1.2)
	Range	0.3 - 10.1	0.3 - 11.9	0.4 - 28.3	0.2 - 8.1	0.2 - 28.3

At the beginning of the final survey, the farmers were asked again if they had purchased the new bean varieties after the training in the previous spring. While we had information about their actual decisions, asking again allowed us to verify that they could recall the varieties properly, show them the bean seeds to receive more reliable responses to the next questions, and assess the saliency of the variables for them. In this regard, the farmers' responses tell us how **committed** they were towards the trial. The responses are reported in Table 34 and Figure 28 for the variety NUA-660. We do not report the distribution for Mashamba PYT-4 because, despite some changes between individual farmers, the values per treatment group are very similar: 64.9% of the farmers declared to have **purchased a new variety**, ranging between 54.2% in T1, and 77.5% in T3. Interestingly, the distribution is quite different from the one deriving from the post-training survey. In that case, the share of purchasers did not differ significantly across the treatment groups. Here, the models (Table 35 for NUA-660 and Table 36 for Mashamba PYT-4) suggest that the **discount** resulted in

a significantly larger percentage of purchasers among T3 farmers. According to some of the models, even the information about **healthiness** and avoided illnesses resulted in significantly higher likelihood of purchasing the new beans compared to the baseline T1, although the effect is much smaller than with the discount.

Table 34: Frequency table of farmers who purchased the new variety NUA-660 (final survey)

Treatment	No	Yes
T1 - Baseline	49	58
T2 - Health info	41	78
T3 - Discount	20	69

Figure 28: Share of farmers who purchased the new variety NUA-660 (final survey)

Table 35: Results of binomial models for those farmers who purchased NUA-660 (final survey)

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	0.17(0.19)	0.16(0.20)	0.17(0.54)	0.22(0.54)
T2 - Health info	0.47(0.27)*	0.46(0.28)	0.52(0.29)*	0.45(0.30)
T3 - Discount	1.07(0.32)***	1.15(0.31)***	1.17(0.34)***	1.19(0.32)***
Age			-0.02(0.01)**	-0.02(0.01)**
Education: Primary or lower			0.43(0.32)	0.48(0.31)
Education: Secondary or higher			0.32(0.49)	0.36(0.48)
Land size (log)			0.26(0.31)	0.18(0.30)
Received loans or credit			0.59(0.32)*	0.59(0.32)*
Association membership			0.79(0.71)	0.72(0.70)
Household size (adults)			0.07(0.10)	0.04(0.10)

Table 36: Binomial models for the farmers who purchased Mashamba PYT-4 (final survey)

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	0.17(0.19)	0.17(0.20)	0.03(0.53)	0.12(0.54)
T2 - Health info	0.51(0.28)*	0.49(0.29)*	0.56(0.29)*	0.49(0.30)
T3 - Discount	1.01(0.32)***	1.08(0.31)***	1.09(0.33)***	1.11(0.32)***
Age			-0.02(0.01)**	-0.02(0.01)**
Education: Primary or lower			0.4(0.31)	0.46(0.31)
Education: Secondary or higher			0.51(0.49)	0.56(0.48)
Land size (log)			0.24(0.31)	0.16(0.30)
Received loans or credit			0.60(0.32)*	0.58(0.32)*
Association membership			0.72(0.71)	0.65(0.70)
Household size (adults)			0.08(0.10)	0.05(0.10)

Farmers were asked to indicate whether they had **grown** the new varieties, and what **land area** they had devoted to each of them. The quantity of seeds provided to each farmer was limited due to the difficulty in multiplying them; therefore, the variability in the land area is also limited. Nevertheless, all the farmers were provided the same quantity of seeds; hence, the land area represents a good proxy of their **commitment and interest**, and is not censored at different points for every farmer. Equally, the demonstration period included two growing seasons, which allowed farmers to multiply the seeds and grow more of them in the following year. The distribution of the areas of land is plotted in Figure 29 for the variety NUA-660, and in Figure 30 for Mashamba PYT-4, and in most instances, it is equal to around 0.25 acres. After implementing a logarithmic transformation to meet the assumption of normality, we estimated the models reported in Table 37 for NUA-660, and in Table 38 for Mashamba PYT-4. Again, we observe that the discount provided to the farmers in T3 resulted in devoting a significantly higher size of land to both varieties, while the healthiness information alone did not yield a significant coefficient. Additionally, having received loans or credit is associated with smaller land sizes devoted to the new varieties. These figures suggest that the lower price paid did not result in lower interest in the new varieties to focus on more valuable ones instead, but probably improved the credibility of the institution providing them (SUA) and the commitment towards the trial as an implicit “agreement” between the latter and the farmer.

Figure 29: Land area devoted to NUA-660 (a), including in logarithmic form (b)

Table 37: Results of linear models of the land area devoted to NUA-660 (logarithmic form)

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-2.24(0.07)**	-2.25(0.07)**	-2.22(0.13)**	-2.2(0.13)**
T2 - Health info	0.02(0.09)	0.03(0.09)	0.03(0.09)	0.04(0.09)
T3 – Discount	0.21(0.09)***	0.2(0.09)***	0.19(0.09)***	0.19(0.09)***
Education: Primary or lower			-0.01(0.09)	-0.01(0.09)
Education: Secondary or higher			-0.14(0.13)	-0.14(0.13)
Land size (log)			0.03(0.05)	0.01(0.05)
Household size (adults)			0.02(0.03)	0.01(0.03)
Received loans or credit			-0.23(0.08)**	-0.21(0.08)**
Association membership			0.01(0.16)	0.02(0.16)

Figure 30: Land area devoted to Mashamba PYT-4 (a), including in logarithmic form (b)

Table 38: Linear models of the land area devoted to Mashamba PYT-4 (logarithmic form)

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-2.23(0.07)***	-2.24(0.07)***	-2.19(0.13)***	-2.17(0.13)***
T2 - Health info	0.02(0.09)	0.02(0.09)	0.03(0.09)	0.03(0.09)
T3 - Discount	0.23(0.09)**	0.22(0.09)**	0.22(0.09)**	0.21(0.09)**
Education: Primary or lower			-0.01(0.10)	-0.02(0.10)
Education: Secondary or higher			-0.06(0.14)	-0.03(0.13)
Land size (log)			0.02(0.05)	0.00(0.05)
Household size (adults)			0.01(0.03)	0.01(0.03)
Received loans or credit			-0.24(0.08)***	-0.22(0.08)***
Association membership			0.01(0.17)	0.01(0.17)

Given the limited variability in the size of land devoted to either of the new varieties, in the following we generate a dummy indicating whether the farmer had **grown** them, and estimate the usual set of models. The percentage of farmers who had grown the new varieties in each treatment group, is shown in Figure 31, and ranges from 57.9% in T1, to 77.5% in T3. Noteworthy, both treatments (information-centred and the discount) seems to have had a positive and significant impact on the likelihood to grow the new varieties. With some differences between the models, the coefficient is around twice as large for T3 (and also significant at 1%, compared to 10% for T2). Moreover, we see that older age is a significant and negative predictor, while having received loans or credit for agriculture is a significant and positive predictor.

Figure 31: Shares of farmers who grew any of the two new varieties

Table 39: Results of binomial models for those farmers who grew any of the two new varieties

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	0.32(0.20)	0.31(0.20)	0.28(0.55)	0.36(0.55)
T2 - Health info	0.48(0.28)*	0.46(0.29)	0.53(0.3)*	0.46(0.31)
T3 – Discount	0.92(0.32)***	1.00(0.31)***	1.01(0.35)***	1.04(0.33)***
Age			-0.02(0.01)**	-0.02(0.01)**
Education: Primary or lower			0.37(0.32)	0.44(0.32)
Education: Secondary or higher			0.27(0.51)	0.33(0.49)
Land size (log)			0.40(0.33)	0.31(0.32)
Received loans or credit			0.72(0.34)**	0.64(0.34)*
Association membership			1.20(0.83)	1.21(0.83)
Household size (adults)			0.05(0.10)	0.02(0.10)

As mentioned above, the new variety **Mashamba PYT-4** was not available to all the farmers who stated to be interested in purchasing it. Therefore, the variable indicating whether they had grown it is censored; to address this issue, we estimate additional models by removing the farmers who had not received the variable after the training. The distribution of the remaining farmers is shown in Figure 32, while model estimates are reported in Table 40. Differently from the models above, the percentage of farmers who grew the variety is exactly the same in the T1 and T2 groups, i.e., two thirds of the total, and higher in the T3 group, at around three quarters. The models show that the 10% discount yielded a positive and significant coefficient, while the information itself did not; additionally, having received credit or loans reduced the likelihood to grow the variety.

Figure 32: Shares of farmers who grew the new variety Mashamba PYT-4, after removing the farmers who had not been assigned it after the training

Table 40: Results of binomial models for those farmers who grew the new variety Mashamba PYT-4, after removing the farmers who had not been assigned it after the training

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-2.24(0.07)***	-2.24(0.07)***	-2.15(0.13)***	-2.14(0.13)***
T2 - Health info	0.02(0.09)	0.03(0.09)	0.04(0.09)	0.05(0.09)
T3 – Discount	0.23(0.09)**	0.22(0.09)**	0.22(0.09)**	0.22(0.09)**
Education: Primary or lower			-0.02(0.10)	-0.03(0.09)
Education: Secondary or higher			-0.1(0.14)	-0.08(0.13)
Land size (log)			0.01(0.05)	-0.01(0.05)
Household size (adults)			0(0.03)	-0.01(0.03)
Received loans or credit			-0.25(0.08)***	-0.24(0.08)***
Association membership			0.05(0.17)	0.05(0.16)

The analysis below focuses on the **consumption side** to assess whether the farmers' households had consumed either of the new bean varieties during the demonstration period. Indeed, although most of the farmers recruited belong to the strata of market-oriented farmers, all of them produce for household consumption too. Given the health benefits potentially generated by the new varieties, we expected that most farmers would consume some of their production, or even part of the seeds received, especially those assigned to treatment T2, who received detailed information on the illnesses that can be avoided with a diet rich in zinc and iron.

The share of farmers whose household consumed either of the new varieties is plotted in Figure 33, and ranges between **11.2%** in the T1 group and **13.5%** in the T3 group. Although the quantity of seeds provided was limited, the impact analysis will later show that some farmers were able to produce enough beans to sell them, especially considered that the demonstration period included two growing seasons. Therefore, these numbers are surprisingly small. Additionally, the models in Table 41 show that there is no significant treatment effect, with farm size being a positive predictor of consumption – larger farmers were probably able to multiply the seeds more effectively, hence having enough of them for their household consumption – and age a negative predictor.

As a robustness check, we cross-tabulate the number of farmers who consumed each of the new varieties separately (Table 42 for NUA-660, and Table 44 for Mashamba PYT-4), and repeat this exercise after removing those farmers who had not purchased the respective variety (Table 46 for NUA-660 and Table 48 for Mashamba PYT-4). We then estimate the same set of models without excluding the farmers who had not purchased the variety (Table 43 for NUA-660, and Table 45 for Mashamba PYT-4) as well as after excluding them (Table 47 for NUA-660, and Table 49 for Mashamba PYT-4). The percentage of consumers increases after those who had not purchased each variety are removed from the sample, as expected. Additionally, this percentage is usually higher for **Mashamba PYT-4**, especially after non-purchasers are removed (16.6%), suggesting that this variety might be more visually **attractive**, and thus more promising also when it comes to selling it. Nevertheless, none of the treatment effects is significant, in any instance, suggesting that the healthiness information does not necessarily result in **healthier eating behaviour** if the recipients of the message are addressed in their capacity of producers. In turn, the farm size and the age of the farmer remain positive and significant and negative and significant predictors of the behaviour.

Figure 33: Shares of farmers who consumed any of the two new varieties

Table 41: Results of binomial models for the farmers who consumed any of the new varieties

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-2.07(0.31)***	-2.03(0.31)***	-2.19(0.79)***	-2.12(0.78)***
T2 - Health info	0.21(0.41)	0.19(0.42)	0.22(0.43)	0.19(0.44)
T3 - Discount	0.21(0.44)	0.22(0.42)	0.32(0.46)	0.31(0.43)
Age			-0.03(0.02)*	-0.03(0.02)*
Education: Primary or lower			0.26(0.48)	0.26(0.47)
Education: Secondary or higher			-0.51(0.77)	-0.23(0.70)
Land size (log)			1.00(0.36)***	0.98(0.36)***
Received loans or credit			0.45(0.38)	0.28(0.38)
Association membership			-0.57(1.10)	-0.61(1.09)
Household size (adults)			0.00(0.14)	0.01(0.14)

Table 42: Frequency table of the farmers who consumed the new variety NUA-660

Treatment	No	Yes	Yes (%)
T1 - Baseline	99	8	7.5%
T2 - Health info	107	12	10.1%
T3 - Discount	78	11	12.4%

Table 43: Results of binomial models for the farmers who consumed the new variety NUA-660

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-2.52(0.37)***	-2.45(0.36)***	-2.86(0.85)***	-2.79(0.84)***
T2 - Health info	0.33(0.48)	0.28(0.49)	0.34(0.49)	0.29(0.49)
T3 - Discount	0.56(0.49)	0.55(0.46)	0.64(0.50)	0.62(0.47)
Age			-0.02(0.02)	-0.02(0.02)
Education: Primary or lower			0.14(0.51)	0.16(0.50)
Education: Secondary or higher			-0.17(0.78)	0.07(0.71)
Land size (log)			0.86(0.38)**	0.89(0.38)**
Received loans or credit			0.31(0.42)	0.09(0.43)
Association membership			-0.39(1.08)	-0.47(1.08)
Household size (adults)			0.08(0.14)	0.08(0.13)

Table 44: Frequency table of farmers who purchased and consumed the new variety NUA-660

Treatment	No	Yes	Yes (%)
T1 - Baseline	50	8	13.8%
T2 - Health info	66	12	15.4%
T3 - Discount	58	11	15.9%

Table 45: Results of binomial models for those farmers who purchased and consumed NUA-660

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-1.83(0.38)**	-1.75(0.38)**	-2.38(0.92)***	-2.34(0.92)***
T2 - Health info	0.13(0.50)	0.08(0.51)	0.21(0.52)	0.15(0.53)
T3 - Discount	0.17(0.51)	0.14(0.48)	0.32(0.53)	0.28(0.51)
Age			-0.02(0.02)	-0.02(0.02)
Education: Primary or lower			-0.16(0.53)	-0.20(0.53)
Education: Secondary or higher			-0.42(0.81)	-0.17(0.74)
Land size (log)			1.02(0.44)***	1.14(0.45)***
Received loans or credit			0.15(0.44)	-0.08(0.45)
Association membership			-0.69(1.14)	-0.82(1.15)
Household size (adults)			0.13(0.15)	0.14(0.14)

Table 46: Frequency table of the farmers who consumed the new variety Mashamba PYT-4

Treatment	No	Yes	Yes (%)
T1 – Baseline	96	11	10.3%
T2 - Health info	105	14	11.8%
T3 – Discount	80	9	10.1%

Table 47: Results of binomial models for farmers who consumed the variety Mashamba PYT-4

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-2.17(0.32)***	-2.14(0.32)***	-2.02(0.8)**	-1.96(0.81)**
T2 - Health info	0.15(0.43)	0.17(0.44)	0.17(0.45)	0.16(0.45)
T3 - Discount	-0.02(0.48)	-0.08(0.46)	0.07(0.49)	-0.01(0.47)
Age			-0.03(0.02)*	-0.03(0.02)*
Education: Primary or lower			0.12(0.48)	0.09(0.47)
Education: Secondary or higher			-1.67(1.12)	-1.82(1.14)
Land size (log)			0.93(0.37)**	0.96(0.37)**
Received loans or credit			0.29(0.41)	0.18(0.42)
Association membership			-0.31(1.1)	-0.28(1.1)
Household size (adults)			0.03(0.14)	0.02(0.14)

Table 48: Frequency table of farmers who purchased and consumed Mashamba PYT-4

Treatment	No	Yes	Yes (%)
T1 – Baseline	47	11	19.0%
T2 - Health info	65	14	17.7%
T3 – Discount	59	9	13.2%

Table 49: Results of binomial models for those farmers who purchased and consumed the new variety Mashamba PYT-4

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-1.45(0.34)***	-1.41(0.34)***	-1.25(0.90)	-1.28(0.91)
T2 - Health info	-0.08(0.45)	-0.05(0.46)	0.09(0.49)	0.09(0.51)
T3 - Discount	-0.43(0.49)	-0.54(0.48)	-0.27(0.53)	-0.36(0.52)
Age			-0.04(0.02)*	-0.03(0.02)*
Education: Primary or lower			-0.18(0.52)	-0.24(0.51)
Education: Secondary or higher			-2.10(1.18)*	-2.23(1.21)*
Land size (log)			1.16(0.45)**	1.24(0.46)***
Received loans or credit			0.16(0.44)	0.04(0.45)
Association membership			-0.53(1.18)	-0.58(1.2)
Household size (adults)			0.07(0.16)	0.09(0.16)

Finally, to assess spillover effects, we asked the farmers whether they had **donated** seeds of any of the new varieties to other farmers (including those assigned to T0, who had not received them). Overall, six farmers (2.9% of those who had bought them) answered that they had donated some seeds. We have no information on whether the recipients had donated seeds further. These numbers are too small to estimate some statistical models, but suggest that there have been **spillover** effects. For instance, for the impact analysis we had to exclude 14 farmers from the baseline group T0 because they had received the seeds, either directly or indirectly.

To conclude this overview of innovation adoption in Tanzania, it is worth spending some words on the **cost of incentivisation**, i.e., the potential “profit” foregone by SUA due to providing 10% more seeds to the farmers in T3 compared to what the quantity would have been if they were paying the price charged in the village for the standard varieties. NUA-660 and Mashamba PYT-4 were never introduced in the market. Hence, we cannot know what their selling prices would be, and we must assume that they would align to the prevailing prices of the standard varieties in the RCT villages. SUA provided to each farmer a standard quantity of 250 grams of seeds, at the price of 500 TZS

(0.19 EUR).⁴ Multiplied by the number of farmers who purchased the seeds, this could have resulted in a theoretical revenue of 230,500 TZS (**85.49 EUR**) if all the seeds were sold at the same price.⁵ However, the farmers in T3 paid 90.9% of the price, hence the actual revenue was 223,955 TZS (83.06 EUR), i.e., 6,454 TZS (**2.39 EUR**) lower, all due to the discount in T3. The saving was 90 TZS (**0.03 EUR**) for each farmer in T3 who purchased the new varieties, which may look negligible but was still enough to trigger the impacts detailed in this section. Hence, a **small and time-limited discount** could promote the uptake of agricultural innovations such as new bean seeds; or at least could **prompt farmers to trial the seeds**, which could then result in large-scale adoption in case of a positive experience.

3.3. Uganda: Upfront payments and payments-by-result

In Uganda, the two dissemination approaches followed for promoting integration between fish and vegetable farming consist respectively in a smaller upfront payment equal to 15% of the cost of setting up the system (**T2 – Upfront pay**), and a larger payment divided into a 5% upfront payment and a 25% payment conditional on achieving pre-set results, namely good water quality parameters (dissolved oxygen >5mg per litre, pH 6.5-9.0, ammonia-N <0.2mg/litre, temperature 24-32°C, fish yield >1.2kg/m²), good vegetable yield, and good visible farm practices (**T3 – Result pay**). The farmers assigned to the latter treatment were informed of the quality criteria, which were then assessed by the enumerators during on-farm visits. The quality criteria were defined by NARO with a view to achieving a positive environmental impact as well as efficient production. Along the process, we registered a number of variables related to adoption. First, the farmers' **interest** in the integrated system, immediately after the training; then, the **submission of business plans**. Indeed, given the high cost of setting up the system relatively to local incomes, and thus the significance of the incentives potentially provided, farmers had to show commitment and planning efforts. The farmers who took part in the training were asked to submit their business plan by a certain date, and were phoned close to the date as a reminder. Then, we register the **actual installation** of the system at the moment of the final survey. However, it must be highlighted that this variable is **self-declared**, and was not verified for the treatment groups T1 and T2, but only for T3, where the enumerators verified the installation on farm. As a result of this complex process, there could be significant **mismatches** between the number of adopters (or potential adopters) registered at different points of the demonstration period. First the farmers who submitted a business plan are not necessarily a subset of those who declared to be interested, as some might have changed their mind after the training, and submitted a business plan even if they had declared not to be interested. Second, some farmers may have changed their mind even after the deadline for submitting the business plan, either by not installing the system despite the submission, or deciding to install it despite not having submitted any business plan. Nevertheless, those who had not submitted a plan were not awarded any **upfront payment**. Third, by design the upfront payment cannot guarantee that the system is actually installed and the project continued; therefore, some of the farmers in T3 who had received the upfront 5% payment were not awarded the 25% **payment by result**. This might well be the case among non-incentivised farmers in T1 who submitted a business plan as well as among the farmers who were awarded the 15% upfront payment in T2, but cannot be verified besides the declaration at the moment of the final survey. Further complications are due to the presence of farmers who had **already installed** a similar system in their farm before the training: these were not excluded from the sample, and were also given the opportunity to receive the payments if assigned to T2 or T3, since adoption was defined as installing a **system that was compliant with the one defined by NARO**, i.e., including pipes, which could differ from the ones already installed by some. Finally,

⁴ The exchange rate used is the mean between the buying and selling rates of the Bank of Tanzania on 24.02.2025 (<https://www.bot.go.tz/ExchangeRate/excRates>).

⁵ We speak of “theoretical” revenue because some farmers paid in kind by exchanging beans or maize.

and for the same **strict definition** of installation, there are cases of farmers who took the message of the training onboard, and started using their aquaculture water to grow vegetables in nearby fields, but without a proper system. When assigned to T3, these farmers were judged as “*non-adopters*” and were not awarded the payment by result, but some of them defined themselves as “*adopters*” in the final survey.

3.3.1. Baseline survey

Like for the other countries, Figure 34 below shows the distribution of individual sample weights in the baseline survey, while descriptive statistics for the control variables are reported in Table 50. Given the sensitiveness of the treatment adopted and the ethical implications of incentivising only a subset of participants, the treatments were assigned to different districts, regardless of the different characteristics of the local fish farmers population. Therefore, the distribution of the farmers among the strata and their socio-demographic characteristics differ significantly between the treatment groups, and the use of sample weights and control variables becomes very important for a correct interpretation of the results.

Figure 34: Sampling weights for the baseline survey for Uganda

Table 50: Descriptive statistics from the baseline survey for Uganda

Variables		T0 (N=107)	T1 (N=111)	T2 (N=91)	T3 (N=107)	Overall (N=416)
Gender	Female	19 (17.8%)	24 (21.6%)	27 (29.7%)	19 (17.8%)	89 (21.4%)
	Male	88 (82.2%)	87 (78.4%)	64 (70.3%)	88 (82.2%)	327 (78.6%)
Education	Illiterate	13 (12.1%)	10 (9.0%)	4 (4.4%)	3 (2.8%)	30 (7.2%)
	Literate, no qualifications	8 (7.5%)	5 (4.5%)	2 (2.2%)	1 (0.9%)	16 (3.8%)
	Primary	36 (33.6%)	36 (32.4%)	15 (16.5%)	21 (19.6%)	108 (26.0%)
	Secondary	38 (35.5%)	31 (27.9%)	27 (29.7%)	32 (29.9%)	128 (30.8%)
Pond size	More than secondary	12 (11.2%)	29 (26.1%)	43 (47.3%)	50 (46.7%)	134 (32.2%)
	Mean (SD)	590.4 (1,352.3)	2,679.1 (11,671.1)	1,411.2 (2,804.7)	1,303.3 (3,493.1)	1,510.6 (6,480.1)
	Median (IQR)	222.9(393.8)	464.5 (998.6)	435.0 (1,436.8)	348.0 (790.3)	371.6 (819.2)
Household size (adults)	Range	1.2 - 11,450	0 - 110,000	0 - 18,120	0 - 30,000	0 - 110,000
	Mean (SD)	4.4 (2.4)	4.0 (2.9)	4.9 (3.2)	4.6 (2.6)	4.4 (2.8)
	Median (IQR)	4.0 (2.0)	3.0 (2.0)	4.0 (3.0)	4.0 (3.0)	4.0 (2.0)
	Range	1.0 - 13.0	1.0 - 27.0	1.0 - 20.0	1.0 - 14.0	1.0 - 27.0

Notes: Due to the small number of farmers who declared to be illiterate or literate but with no qualifications, these groups were merged with those with primary education before proceeding. Equally, for each categorical variable, one level will be omitted for collinearity reasons, thus representing the baseline.

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As a first step, after the training, the fish farmers were asked if they would be **interested** in installing the systems for integrating fish and vegetable farming in their farm. As shown in Figure 35 below, a large percentage responded “yes, definitely”, followed by “probably yes”. These two responses were used to create a dummy variable and estimate the set of binomial models presented in Table 51 below. The farmers assigned to T2 were more likely to respond “yes, definitely” (79%), compared to those in T3 (64%) or in T1 (53%), but the difference, when the responses are turned into a dummy, is not statistically significant.

Figure 35: Would you be interested in installing the system in your farm by the deadline set?

Table 51: Results of binomial models for those farmers who declared to be interested

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	1.29(0.23)***	1.33(0.24)***	3.34(1.06)***	3.4(1.07)***
T2 - Upfront pay	0.42(0.37)	0.27(0.36)	0.48(0.41)	0.34(0.39)
T3 - Result pay	-0.15(0.32)	-0.19(0.34)	-0.01(0.36)	-0.12(0.37)
Age			-0.02(0.01)	-0.01(0.01)
Gender: Male			-0.43(0.40)	-0.25(0.39)
Education: Primary or lower			-0.28(0.84)	-0.18(0.84)
Education: Secondary			-0.46(0.84)	-0.35(0.83)
Education: Above secondary			-1.23(0.81)	-1.20(0.81)
Pond size (log)			-0.11(0.07)	-0.17(0.08)**
Household size (adults)			0.10(0.06)	0.10(0.06)

As a robustness check, we re-ran the above models after removing 24 farmers who had a **similar system already installed** in their farm; the model estimates are reported in Table 52 below. In line with the previous estimates, we observe no significant treatment effects. Interestingly, the stated level of interest is significantly negatively correlated with the size of the fish farm (i.e., of the ponds), suggesting that smaller farmers might have seen the innovation as a way to increase their revenue in the presence of constraint relative to pond size.

Table 52: Results of binomial models for those farmers who declared to be interested, after removing the farmers who had a system already installed

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	1.63(0.27)***	1.69(0.28)***	3.87(1.40)***	4.25(1.47)***
T2 - Upfront pay	0.77(0.48)	0.46(0.44)	0.70(0.51)	0.42(0.48)
T3 - Result pay	-0.01(0.38)	-0.05(0.40)	0.01(0.42)	-0.09(0.44)
Age			-0.01(0.01)	0.00(0.01)
Gender: Male			-0.22(0.47)	0.04(0.45)
Education: Primary or lower			-0.77(1.13)	-0.81(1.22)
Education: Secondary			-0.86(1.13)	-0.93(1.21)
Education: Above secondary			-1.15(1.12)	-1.30(1.20)
Pond size (log)			-0.17(0.10)*	-0.27(0.10)***
Household size (adults)			0.05(0.07)	0.06(0.07)

The farmers who declared not to be interested in installing the system by the deadline set by NARO, were asked whether they would be **interested** in doing so **“in the future.”** Their responses were merged with the responses to the previous question, obtaining the distribution reported in Table 53 and Figure 36 below, which provides an overview of the farmers’ interest in installing the system either in the short-term, or at some point in the future. The variable was turned into a dummy that takes value 1 if the farmers responded *“yes, definitely”*, which was then used to estimate the models in Table 54. In line with our expectation, the farmers assigned to treatment groups with incentives declare a higher interest than those assigned to the baseline T1. More precisely, the highest level of interest is observed among those assigned to T2 (smaller upfront payment). The difference is still significant if including the control variables and using sample weights; hence, it is not driven by other factors.

Table 53: Interest in installing the system either before the deadline or at some point in the future

Treatment	Definitely not	Probably not	Not sure / Difficult to say	Probably yes	Yes, definitely
T1 - Baseline	2	0	5	1 (36)	4 (56)
T2 - Upfront pay	0	1	0	1 (14)	2 (66)
T3 - Result pay	1	0	2	2 (23)	8 (68)

Note: The values in parentheses represent the number of farmers who selected each response after integrating the responses to the previous question. The first three levels of the Likert scale remain unchanged.

Figure 36: Would you be interested in installing the system in your farm now or in the future?

Table 54: Binomial models for interest in installing the system now or in the future

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	0.26(0.2)	0.25(0.21)	-0.04(0.87)	0.02(0.88)
T2 - Upfront pay	1.22(0.35)***	1.25(0.34)***	1.09(0.38)***	1.21(0.38)***
T3 - Result pay	0.70(0.31)**	0.77(0.32)**	0.53(0.33)	0.70(0.34)**
Age			0.00(0.01)	-0.01(0.01)
Gender: Male			0.46(0.33)	0.52(0.34)
Education: Primary or lower			0.22(0.60)	0.26(0.62)
Education: Secondary			0.17(0.60)	-0.03(0.62)
Education: Above secondary			0.82(0.61)	0.64(0.63)
Pond size (log)			-0.05(0.07)	-0.01(0.07)
Household size (adults)			0.02(0.05)	0.04(0.06)

The following step for the farmers interested in integrating fish and vegetable farming was to **submit a business plan** by the deadline set by NARO. The business plan was a simple document aimed at registering interest in a more formal way, and allowing NARO to provide advice and, depending on the treatment, support, and monitoring. Overall, 8 out of 309 farmers (**27.5%**) submitted a business plan. However, this overall percentage hides large differences between the treatment groups, as shown in Table 55 and Figure 37. The binomial model estimates reported in Table 56 show that these differences are statistically significant, with the farmers assigned to T3 being by far the most likely to submit a business plan (49.5%) and those assigned to T2 the least likely (12.1%), while the baseline group T1 lies slightly above the latter (18.9%). These figures suggest that the larger **payment by result** proved attractive to the farmers despite the entailed risk, while the 15% **upfront payment** may have been perceived as too small, thus crowding out intrinsic motivations or raising expectations of future larger payments. Moreover, it is worth noting that the farmers assigned to T2 had expressed the highest level of interest but then submitted the smallest number of business plans. This mismatch points out to the **unreliability of stated preferences** detected by means of questionnaires, especially when dealing with innovations that entail large investment costs but generate socially desirable environmental outcomes.

Table 55: Frequency table of the farmers who submitted a business plan by the deadline

Treatment	No	Yes
T1 – Baseline	90	21
T2 - Upfront pay	80	11
T3 - Result pay	54	53

Figure 37: Shares of farmers who submitted a business plan by the deadline

Table 56: Results of binomial models for farmers who submitted a business plan by the deadline

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-1.46(0.24)***	-1.44(0.25)***	-3.39(1.04)***	-3.19(1.03)***
T2 - Upfront pay	-0.53(0.40)	-0.34(0.38)	-0.57(0.43)	-0.44(0.40)
T3 - Result pay	1.44(0.31)***	1.56(0.32)***	1.33(0.33)***	1.43(0.34)***
Age			0.03(0.01)***	0.03(0.01)**
Gender: Male			0.14(0.35)	0.14(0.35)
Education: Primary or lower			0.87(0.83)	0.80(0.82)
Education: Secondary			1.01(0.83)	0.93(0.82)
Education: Above secondary			0.99(0.82)	1.05(0.81)
Pond size (log)			-0.07(0.07)	-0.06(0.07)
Household size (adults)			-0.03(0.05)	-0.05(0.05)

As a robustness check, we re-run the above models after removing again the 24 farmers who had a similar **system already installed** in their farm. The distribution of business plan submissions is shown in Figure 38, while the model estimates are reported in Table 57. The results above hold, and the coefficients become even larger, as 48.5% of the farmers in the T3 group submitted a business plan, compared to 10.7% in T2, and 19.2% in T1. Therefore, the recruitment criteria and the incentivisation scheme did **not** result in **moral hazard**, as they did not end up incentivising farmers who would have installed the system anyway or already had a more advanced farm compared to others; or at least, it did not systematically benefit those farmers. Moreover, **age** emerged as a significant positive predictor of the business plan submission, suggesting that more experienced farmers felt more comfortable to embark in this type of project.

Figure 38: Shares of farmers that submitted a business plan and do not have the system

Table 57: Results of binomials models for those farmers who submitted a business plan and do not have the system

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-1.44(0.25)***	-1.41(0.26)***	-3.55(1.08)***	-3.30(1.06)***
T2 - Upfront pay	-0.69(0.43)	-0.46(0.40)	-0.70(0.46)	-0.56(0.42)
T3 - Result pay	1.37(0.32)***	1.49(0.33)***	1.31(0.34)***	1.40(0.35)***
Age			0.04(0.01)***	0.03(0.01)***
Gender: Male			0.02(0.37)	0.07(0.36)
Education: Primary or lower			0.82(0.83)	0.76(0.83)
Education: Secondary			1.06(0.83)	0.97(0.83)
Education: Above secondary			0.90(0.83)	0.99(0.82)
Pond size (log)			-0.06(0.08)	-0.05(0.07)
Household size (adults)			-0.04(0.06)	-0.05(0.06)

3.3.2. Final survey

The variables discussed in the following refer to the final survey, i.e., they were gathered at the end of the demonstration period and therefore, reflect more precisely the real adoption behaviour of the fish farmers involved. Compared to the other two countries, **attrition** was higher, at **23.1%**, reflecting the difficulty in conducting the RCT across several districts, and the smaller eligible population compared to crop farmers. The fish farmers who took part in the training but did not show up at the final survey and could not be found despite the many attempts conducted by the enumerators, are considered “*non-adopters*.” These include three farmers assigned to T3 who had received the 5% upfront payment, pointing to the **risk of providing upfront payments** not conditioned to the achievement of specific objectives.

Sample weights were calculated for the final survey too, and are plotted in Figure 39, while Table 58 shows that the characteristics of the farmers still differs significantly between the treatment groups, especially in terms of size of the fish production system, requiring the use of sample weights and control variables.

Figure 39: Sampling weights for the final survey for Uganda

Table 58: Descriptive statistics from the final survey for Uganda

Variables	T0 (N=105)	T1 (N=73)	T2 (N=63)	T3 (N=79)	Overall (N=320)	
Education	Illiterate	11 (10.5%)	7 (9.6%)	5 (7.9%)	4 (5.1%)	27 (8.4%)
	Literate with no qualifications	7 (6.7%)	10 (13.7%)	2 (3.2%)	1 (1.3%)	20 (6.2%)
	Primary	39 (37.1%)	22 (30.1%)	7 (11.1%)	18 (22.8%)	86 (26.9%)
	Secondary	30 (28.6%)	19 (26.0%)	20 (31.7%)	21 (26.6%)	90 (28.1%)
	More than secondary	18 (17.1%)	15 (20.5%)	29 (46.0%)	35 (44.3%)	97 (30.3%)
Age	Mean (SD)	48.2 (13.6)	49.6 (13.8)	48.5 (14.8)	49.9 (13.4)	49.0 (13.8)
	Median (IQR)	50.0 (23.0)	45.0 (18.0)	49.0 (22.0)	51.0 (19.5)	49.0 (21.0)
	Range	22.0 - 76.0	24.0 - 82.0	18.0 - 90.0	22.0 - 83.0	18.0 - 90.0
Pond size	Mean (SD)	595.7 (1,364.2)	2,613.8 (12,910.1)	1,172.3 (2,087.2)	1,580.4 (4,021.1)	1,414.2 (6,621.3)
	Median (IQR)	222.9 (376.9)	471.0 (977.0)	524.0 (1,393.0)	400.0 (803.5)	374.7 (799.7)
	Range	1.2 - 11,450	18.6 - 110,000	0 - 13,000	0 - 30,000	0 - 110,000
	Missing	0	0	2 (3.2%)	0	2 (0.6%)
Household size (adults)	Mean (SD)	4.8 (2.4)	3.9 (2.1)	4.3 (2.5)	4.3 (2.2)	4.4 (2.3)
	Median (IQR)	5.0 (3.0)	4.0 (3.0)	4.0 (4.0)	4.0 (2.0)	4.0 (4.0)
	Range	1.0 - 12.0	1.0 - 11.0	1.0 - 13.0	1.0 - 14.0	1.0 - 14.0

In the final survey, the farmers were asked whether they had installed the system integrating the fish and vegetable farming in their farm. According to NARO’s definition, **adoption proper** required the installation of pipes to allow reuse of aquaculture wastewater for irrigating the vegetables. However, this was only checked for the farmers in T3 who had submitted a business plan and had received the upfront 5% payment. For other farmers, the only information available is their response to the respective question in the final survey. While this is not 100% accurate, it reflects the usual situation faced by policymakers when incentivising or promoting the uptake of agri-environmental practices by farmers, whereby direct monitoring is too costly or difficult. As a result, some farmers may have declared that they have adopted even if they have not followed NARO’s instructions in full (including some who were denied the payment by result for this reason), if they perceive that they are integrating fish and vegetable farming. Their responses are retained. In turn, some of the farmers in T2 who received the upfront 15% payment may have declared not to have adopted, because indeed they used the money for other purposes. The only case where we expect a full correspondence between **stated adoption and actual adoption**, is for those farmers who had received the payment-by-results following a positive assessment of the outcome. As already mentioned earlier on, some producers had a similar system already installed in their farms, and were retained in the sample, but this situation is documented through two options provided in the question. Using these options, we derive two definitions of **adopters**, used for the impact analysis, and corresponding **adoption rates**. First, if we consider as adopters both those who started from nothing, and those who had a similar system already in place, the adoption rate is **13.9%** (43 out of 309), while if we exclude the latter, it is **10.7%** (32 out of 298)⁶. The distribution of adopters and non-adopters across the treatment groups is provided in Table 59 and illustrated in Figure 40, while the regressions models are reported in Table 60. Noteworthy, the adoption rates do not differ significantly depending on the incentivisation scheme – only the size of the system (ponds) is positively and marginally related to adoption in one of the models. Hence, assuming that farmers’ stated adoption reflects their **real behaviour** in T2 and T3, the incentives were not successful in promoting wider uptake of the innovation. However, the upfront incentive and, even more, the incentive by result may well have resulted in **stronger commitment** in the implementation of the innovation by recipient farmers and, therefore, better results – something we cannot verify comparatively with our data and that would require further research.

Table 59: Have you installed the system in your fish farm?

Treatment	No	Yes, before the training	Yes, after the training
T1 - Baseline	97	2	12
T2 - Upfront pay	81	2	8
T3 - Result pay	88	7	12

Figure 40: Have you installed the system in your fish farm?

⁶ We consider those who do not respond to the final survey as “non-adopters”.

Table 60: Results of binomial models for the farmers who did install the system

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-1.94(0.29)***	-1.99(0.30)***	-4.47(1.35)***	-4.46(1.41)***
T2 - Upfront pay	-0.16(0.44)	0.04(0.43)	-0.07(0.47)	0.04(0.45)
T3 - Result pay	0.40(0.38)	0.39(0.40)	0.47(0.41)	0.40(0.43)
Age			0.02(0.01)	0.02(0.01)
Gender: Male			-0.38(0.40)	-0.36(0.40)
Education: Primary or lower			1.20(1.09)	1.14(1.18)
Education: Secondary			0.99(1.10)	1.15(1.18)
Education: Above secondary			0.94(1.09)	1.11(1.17)
Pond size (log)			0.15(0.09)*	0.13(0.09)
Household size (adults)			0.00(0.06)	0.02(0.06)

As a robustness check, we re-ran the above analysis after **removing** the farmers who had a similar system already installed in their farm before the training. The distribution by treatment group is reported in Table 61 and illustrated in Figure 41, while the model estimates are provided in Table 62. The results are very similar to the previous ones: the adoption rate is highest in T3 (13.3%) and lowest in T2 (8.5%), compared to a baseline of 11.8%, but these differences are not statistically significant.

Table 61: Frequency table of the farmers who installed the system after the training only

Treatment	No	Yes
T1 - Baseline	90	12
T2 - Upfront pay	75	7
T3 - Result pay	78	12

Figure 41: Shares of farmers who installed the system after the training only

Table 62: Results of binomial models for farmers who installed the system after the training only

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	-1.94(0.29)***	-1.99(0.30)***	-4.47(1.35)***	-4.46(1.41)***
T2 - Upfront pay	-0.16(0.44)	0.04(0.43)	-0.07(0.47)	0.04(0.45)
T3 - Result pay	0.40(0.38)	0.39(0.40)	0.47(0.41)	0.40(0.43)
Age			0.02(0.01)	0.02(0.01)
Gender: Male			-0.38(0.40)	-0.36(0.40)
Education: Primary or lower			1.20(1.09)	1.14(1.18)
Education: Secondary			0.99(1.10)	1.15(1.18)
Education: Above secondary			0.94(1.09)	1.11(1.17)
Pond size (log)			0.15(0.09)*	0.13(0.09)
Household size (adults)			0.00(0.06)	0.02(0.06)

The farmers who had adopted the innovation were asked whether they intended to **maintain and keep using** the integrated fish and vegetable farming system in future production cycles. Their responses, reported in Table 63, were all positive, with 79% of the farmers answering that they were “very likely” to maintain and keep using it and slightly higher levels of satisfaction among T2 and T3 farmers – probably an indirect impact of the incentive.

Table 63: Likelihood of maintaining and keeping using the system in the future

Treatment	Likely	Very likely
T1 – Baseline	4	10
T2 - Upfront pay	1	9
T3 - Result pay	4	15

Also in Uganda, we can make some considerations regarding the **cost of incentivisation**. Due to the high cost of the innovation and the use of financial incentives rather than information-centred nudges, this is relatively high compared to the other two countries. The total expenditure for the incentives was **56,922,390 UGX (14,843 EUR)**⁷. This includes **5,709 EUR** of upfront incentives in T2 (571 EUR per adopter on average), and **9,134 EUR** of upfront and ex-post incentives in T3. In particular, 20 farmers in T3 received the 5% upfront payment only, for a total of **1,052 EUR** (53 EUR on average), while 23 received both the 5% upfront payment and the 25% payment by result, for a total of **8,083 EUR** (351 EUR on average). These figures suggest that the sum requested by the farmers in T2 was larger on average. In addition to these costs, NARO had to invest some resources to visit the fish farms of the farmers assigned to T3 who had received the upfront incentive, in order to verify whether they had achieved the result. Unfortunately, the resources available and the nature of the incentivisation scheme did not allow to verify adoption and the quality of implementation in all the treatment groups, including the baseline. Therefore, we cannot know if the incentives resulted in better implementation, or run a cost-benefit analysis. However, we know that in T3, 47% of the farmers who had received the upfront payment (20 out of 43) either did not install the system or did not manage it properly, despite knowing that there would be a **monitoring phase**. This percentage could be higher in T1 and T2, where no monitoring was foreseen.

⁷ The exchange rate used is the average between the Bank of Uganda buying and selling rates on 20.02.2025 (<https://www.bou.or.ug/bouwebsite/bouwebsitecontent/ExchangeRates/scripts.MajorExchangeRates/index.jsp?year=2025&month=Feb&day=20>).

4. Analysis of impact

This section analyses the **impact** of the three innovations on farm performance and the wellbeing of the farming household. Compared to the analysis of adoption in Section 3 above, this analysis is necessarily less robust because of the **short demonstration period**, which was constrained by the timeline of the FoodLAND project. Although the demonstration period covered an entire farming year or aquaculture production cycle, using the innovations for longer time would have allowed to draw more robust conclusions concerning the **causal effects** of the innovations themselves. For instance, in Tanzania, we asked the farmers to list the diet-related diseases experienced by their households; however, the consumption of zinc- and iron-rich beans cannot generate a meaningful impact in this regard within less than one year, also because of the small quantity of seed provided.

In this section of the report, the samples from each country case study are divided in two treatment groups: **non-adopters (baseline or control)**, represented by the farmers assigned to **T0**, who received no innovations during the initial training (although the innovation was provided to them too after the final survey for ethical and fairness reasons); and **adopters (or treated)**, i.e., all the farmers assigned to T1, T2, and T3 who had adopted the innovation, pulled together. Besides attrition, which reduced the number of usable observations, the size of the baseline group was also reduced due to spillovers, e.g., receiving the new bean varieties from treated farmers in Tanzania, or receiving the link to download the phone app in Morocco. In turn, the treated are **self-selected**, i.e., include only the farmers who adopted the innovations, which could have been driven by systematic differences between them and non-adopters from the same treatment groups. Therefore, the randomisation is not fully valid anymore, and the different outcomes between adopters and non-adopters may be driven by other farmer characteristics rather than by the innovations.

To overcome the above challenges, we assess the impact of the innovations using a **difference-in-differences (DID)** approach, whereby the change in the value of the variables of interest (indicators of farm performance and household wellbeing) between the baseline and the final surveys for the treated group (adopters) is compared to the change in the same variables for the baseline group (non-adopters).⁸ This approach allows to isolate from the effect of other variables that may have impacted both groups in the same way at the same point in time (e.g., if one of the two agricultural years was characterised by lower yields due to unfavourable climatic conditions, the difference-in-differences approach allows to assess the impact of the innovation net of the impact of the climatic conditions) as well as from the characteristics of the individual farmer. The difference is calculated as follows, where V is the variable of interest, b indicates the baseline survey, and f the final one: $\Delta V_{b,f} = V_f - V_b$. We test the null hypothesis $H_0: \Delta V_{b,f_a} - \Delta V_{b,f_n} = 0$, where a indicates adopters and n non-adopters. The statistical test used depends on the typology of variable: t -test if the assumption of normality is verified, Wilcoxon or Kruskal-Wallis tests otherwise.

To facilitate interpretation of the DID results, in Table 64 below we show the structure of the tables reporting them, which will be maintained constant along the whole section, and the explanation of the single elements. For example, a positive value in the column “*Diff. in diff.*” would indicate that the adopters have experienced a change in “*Variable*” that is larger than for non-adopters (if “*Diff. final – baseline Adopters*” is positive) or “less negative” (if “*Diff. final – baseline Adopters*” is positive); a negative value would indicate that the adopters have experienced a change that is smaller than for non-adopters (if “*Diff. final – baseline Adopters*” is positive) or “more negative” (if “*Diff. final – baseline Adopters*” is positive).

⁸ Abadie, A. (2005). Semiparametric difference-in-differences estimators. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 72(1): 1-19.

Table 64: structure of the tables presenting the DID results

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
The variable object of analysis; there could be a further column specifying a variable grouping	Number of observations repeated in both surveys	Mean value and standard deviation of the variable in the baseline survey	Mean value and standard deviation of the variable in the final survey	Mean difference between the values in the final and baseline survey for non-adopters	Mean difference between the values in the final and baseline survey for adopters	Mean difference between the differences (adopters minus non-adopters)	Statistic associated to the difference in the differences	p-value associated to the statistic

As robustness checks, in the final survey we asked farmers about their **perceived change** in key variables, such as yields or the quantity of farm inputs used, and whether they thought that these changes were **caused by the innovation**. Such variables are assessed by means of Likert scales (e.g., from “much lower” to “much higher” yields, or from “no impact” to “extremely impactful”). For these variables, we lack a pre-demonstration value. Hence, when dealing with perceived change, we only test if the responses differ significantly between non-adopters and adopters, while for the variables concerning the possible impact of the innovation, we test if the adopters’ responses are significantly different from “probably not” or similar responses suggesting no impact.

In terms of **outcome variables**, the following aspects will be assessed in all the countries:

1. *Farm product*: land size, yields, sales (quantity and value), losses, self-consumption – overall and for specific crops (or varieties, or fish species) addressed by the innovations;
2. *Farm inputs*: quantity used and cost – overall and for specific inputs that we assume can be impacted by the innovations;
3. *Farm profits*: difference between the total value of production and the cost of inputs, for crop and fish farming separately, where relevant;
4. *Household incomes and expenses*: farm sales, farm expenses, energy costs, as aggregates, also as a robustness check;
5. *Farm practices*: irrigation, soil fertility, etc.

Additionally, in specific countries, and depending on the features and goals of the innovations considered, we will also assess indicators of **crop diversity** (e.g., number of vegetables grown by fish farmers in Uganda) and **dietary diversity** (e.g., number of vegetables consumed in Uganda, bean consumption in Tanzania). In Tanzania, we also ask about diet-related diseases, and food preparation practices (fuel use). Finally, for what concerns farm production and input use, we ask our farmers (treated and control groups) if they had **perceived any change** compared to the previous farming season and, to adopters who declared a significant change, whether they believe that the change is due to the innovation.

4.1. Morocco: Phone app for precision irrigation and protection

In **Morocco**, the sample size for the impact analysis, reported in Table 1 in Section 1.2, is represented by **248** farmers, including 164 adopters (66.1%) and 84 non-adopters. The largest number of adopters (69, 42.0%) belong to T3, followed by T2 (53, 32.3%), and T1 (25.6%). A more restrictive definition of adopters, excluding the farmers who made “minimum acceptable use” of the app, would result in a sample size of 239, of which 155 adopters (64.9%). Nevertheless, in this Section we use the broader definition of adopter as anyone who did “minimal” or “optimal” use of the app. The farmers were recruited for being **carrot, onion, or potato** growers, and indeed, the number of those who grew any of these vegetables at least once between the baseline and final surveys are 208 (34.9% of all the potential occurrences) for potatoes, 196 (32.9%) for onions, and 13 (2.2%) for carrots. Due to the limited number of carrot growers, no crop-specific analysis is implemented.

As a first step, in Table 65 below we show the DID results in terms of **production** and **sales** of the key crops, while the box plots of the difference between the baseline and final values of the same variables for non-adopters and adopter are shown in Figure 42. As expected given the short duration of the demonstration and the need for farmers to train themselves with the phone app, we registered limited significant changes between the two growing seasons. In most cases, the farmers (adopters and non-adopters) experienced a decline in production, with a consequent drop in the quantity and value of sales (the value of production is inclusive of the self-consumed quantity). The only significant difference is observed in the **onion yield** per hectare: adopters experienced a smaller decline, 10.3 instead of 14.8 tons, which may be due to their improved irrigation practices.

Table 65: Farm production variables in Morocco

Crop	Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
carrots	production value (1,000 MAD)	11	113.4(51.2)	69.4(75.4)					
	sales value (1,000 MAD)	11	100.7(53.4)	57.2(64.5)					
onions	land (ha)	183	1.4(1.1)	1.1(1.2)	-0.187	-0.251	0.065	0.502	0.617
	quantity produced (tons)	191	80.1(62.3)	66.8(62)	-13.250	-13.225	-0.025	-0.004	0.997
	yield (tons/ha)	193	59.1(18)	47.4(29.4)	-14.820	-10.320	4.500	4.917	0.027
	production value (1,000 MAD)	185	238.3(200.9)	172.8(163.2)	-57.790	-68.859	11.069	0.522	0.603
	sales quantity (tons)	191	75.1(59.0)	60.1(56.6)	-15.183	-15.007	0.176	0.030	0.976
	sales value (1,000 MAD)	183	215.5(176.4)	150.6(143.2)	-61.091	-66.588	-5.497	-0.279	0.781
potatoes	land (ha)	170	1.3(0.9)	1.0(0.0)	-0.429	-0.220	-0.209	-1.467	0.145
	quantity produced (tons)	203	58.1(46.5)	44.2(23.1)	-8.116	-16.892	-8.776	-1.342	0.181
	yield (tons/ha)	200	44.0(17.8)	43.6(21.9)	5.200	-3.450	-8.650	-2.493	0.114
	production value (1,000 MAD)	192	215.4(179)	128.2(83.6)	-78.724	-91.798	-13.074	-0.506	0.613
	sales quantity (tons)	204	52.1(41.6)	39.6(21.5)	-8.768	-14.393	-5.624	-0.947	0.345
	sales value (1,000 MAD)	192	197.6(168)	114(78.5)	-75.999	-87.692	-11.694	-0.485	0.628

Note: The dataset includes several instances of sales above production; preliminary checks revealed that the quantities of sales had been multiplied 10-fold compared to the quantity of production, and the mismatch could be solved by dividing them accordingly; two remaining instances of sales above production were set as equal to the quantity produced.

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Figure 42: Box plots of farm production variables in Morocco

After having discussed the production side, we focus on the use of inputs. Farmers were asked to indicate their input use for only one of the three crops, and to report at least one value between the total cost and the quantity. In Table 66 below reports the aggregate figure (across the three crops) for the three inputs more likely to be affected by the use of the app (weed killer, energy, and water for irrigation), as well as the total cost of inputs (not only those listed); the box plots with the DID are shown in Figure 43 instead. In line with the drop in production observed previously, we register a drop in input use and expenditure across the board. However, noteworthy, the drop in the quantity of **water and energy** use and in the expense for irrigation water is significantly larger among adopters (the total input cost does not differ significantly between the two groups, anyway). More precisely, they register an average reduction of 1,199 litres of water used, compared to 898 litres.

Table 66: Farm input variables in Morocco⁹

Input	Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Input quantity	Weed killer	235	2.3(1.3)	2.6(1.5)	0.10	0.35	0.25	1.917	0.166
	Energy	205	133.3(40.1)	90.2(59.9)	-29.06	-50.22	-21.16	4.648	0.031
	Water	175	2,264.7(953.2)	1,147.9(1,062.2)	-898.33	-1,199.42	-301.09	3.142	0.076
Input costs (1,000 MAD)	Weed killer	242	1.0(0.8)	0.9(0.6)	-0.18	-0.02	0.16	1.869	0.172
	Energy	223	4.7(3.4)	3.5(3.0)	-1.78	-0.95	0.83	0.865	0.352
	Water	180	2.4(1.2)	1.3(1.3)	-0.67	-1.25	-0.58	-4.102	0.043
Total cost (1,000 MAD)		234	50.2(24.7)	38.9(18.8)	8.599	12.631	4.031	1.139	0.256

⁹ For Morocco as well as for other countries, the farmers were asked to indicate at least one figure between the total cost and the quantity of each input. In the analysis, we retain all the occurrences where at least one of the two is non-missing, and larger than zero. For example, the price can be zero if the input was provided for free, and these instances are not treated as missing values; instead, no instances of zero quantities were observed in case of a positive price (if the quantity was unknown, it was registered as missing).

Figure 43: Box plots of farm input variables in Morocco

Table 67: Farm profit by crop in Morocco¹⁰

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Carrots	3	-7.5(54.3)	-43.4(13.5)					
Onions	73	-15.1(51.3)	-31.3(20.0)	-5.648	-20.455	-14.806	-1.319	0.193
Potatoes	158	28.1(81.5)	6.9(69.3)	-19.486	-22.227	-2.741	-0.179	0.858

Note: The profits and their differences across groups are reported in 1,000 MAD.

Figure 44: Box plots of farm profit by crop in Morocco

Based on the above production and expenditure figures, we calculated crop-specific farm **profits**, which are reported in Table 67 above and further illustrated (for onions and potatoes) in Figure 44. We cannot calculate an overall farm profit since the costs of inputs declared refer to a single crop;

¹⁰ For Morocco as well as for other countries, farm profits are obtained as the difference between the value of *production* and the cost of inputs. While most Moroccan farmers are market-oriented, this is not always the case, and self-consumption can represent a significant share of the farm's produce. We thus decided to use the value of production instead of sales, as this is a better proxy of how farming benefits household wellbeing.

therefore, the production values used in the calculations also refer to that crop only. We observe a (positive) profit for potatoes and a loss for onions in both surveys, with a worsening between the two growing seasons. This worsening is wider for adopters, who lose 14,806 MAD more than non-adopters on average when growing onions, and earn 2,741 MAD less for potatoes. Nevertheless, none of these differences-in-differences is statistically significant.

Moroccan farmers are assigned **water right hours** based on the characteristics of their farm and the crops grown. ENAM argued that the **efficient irrigation practices** favoured by the use the app could result in a reduced water needs and thus also a reduced need of irrigation hours (which are used as an alternative to actual quantification due to the lack of water metres). In turn, the farmers could in theory generate more income by selling their water hours, or cede these to other farmers for free. However, the DID estimates in Table 68, further illustrated through box plots in Figure 45, suggest that no significant change in this regard took place: all the farmers experienced reduction in water hours between the two surveys, and adopters a greater reduction by two hours per week, but the difference with non-adopters is not statistically significant. Farmers' responses to another related question ("*Have you sold or transferred part of your irrigation rights?*") showed that 86.7% of them (215 out of 248) either had not considered this possibility or were not interested, while the other 13.3% stated that it was not possible to sell them, with no difference depending on adoption.

Table 68: Water right hours for irrigation per month in Morocco

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Water rights hours	243	202.6(275.6)	196.0(238.4)	-5.345	-7.236	-1.880	0.650	0.419

Figure 45: Box plots of water right hours for irrigation in Morocco

Figure 46: Were you able to expand the area under irrigated crops due to the fact that you followed the instructions provided by the application?

As an alternative, the farmers who followed the instructions provided in the app, might have used less water for irrigating the same area of land, thus being able to **expand** their **irrigated surfaces** at parity of water use. In the final survey, we asked if this was the case, and the farmers' responses are reported in Figure 46 above. A large majority of the farmers (84.7%) reported at least a slight increase in the surface irrigated; therefore, the responses differ significantly from "no" ($p < 0.001$).

Two other aspects that could be affected if following the instructions provided in the app are the relative importance of different **water sources** for irrigation, and the implementation of **soil fertilisation practices**. In both the baseline and final surveys, farmers were asked to rank their water sources, and to select all the practices implemented. Table 69 below reports the results in terms of ranking, and the count of the soil fertilisation practices implemented. These variables are quite constant across the two surveys: we observe limited temporal change, and no significant difference depending on adoption.

Table 69: Ranking of water sources, and number of soil fertilisation practices, in Morocco

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Spring	248	1.2(2.1)	1.2(2.2)	0.060	0.085	-0.026	0.139	0.709
Canals	248	1.6(2.3)	1.6(2.3)	0.048	-0.024	-0.072	0.000	0.993
Underground (well)	248	2.5(2.5)	2.4(2.5)	0.012	-0.012	-0.024	0.094	0.759
Common tanks	248	0.1(0.8)	0.1(0.5)	-0.119	-0.043	0.076	0.494	0.482
Soil fertilisation practices (number)	248	2.4(1.2)	2.5(1.2)	0.100	0.110	0.010	0.310	0.576

Notes: Farmers were asked to rank all water sources with 1 being the most important and 5 the least important. To implement the analysis, a value of 5 was assigned to the most important, 1 to the least important, and 0 to the sources not ranked.

Besides precision irrigation and fertigation, another function of the app was to provide warnings if the local conditions could potentially result in outbreak of potato late blight (**precision protection**). In both surveys, farmers were asked to report the late blight outbreaks in their farm and then if the warnings embedded in the app generated some benefits in this regard. Unfortunately (for our test, but luckily for the farmers), there was no late blight outbreak in the implementation year; therefore, no farmer answered the respective questions. In the initial survey, 88.6% of the farmers who grew potatoes reported **late blight outbreaks** in the previous year, with no significant difference based on their future adoption status; as expected, no one reported outbreaks in the final survey. When asked if they had seen any improvement in terms of blight outbreaks, 75.0% of the potato growers responded that it had been light, or non-existent, and 22.7% that it was difficult to say (due to the absence of outbreaks), with no differences between adopters and non-adopters.

We have discussed the variables derived from actual measurements or from recalling quantitative values. Now, we will focus on farmers' **self-assessments** of production practices and outcomes. While such responses could be more subject to estimation errors, they are still significant because farmers tend to make their decisions based on perceptions rather than actual outcomes, which in many cases (e.g., the quantification of water uses) are also the results of rough estimations since most farmers do not keep books, or do not have the systems to make direct measurements. Table 70 and Figure 47 below report DID estimates of the farmers' self-assessment of **yield change** for the three key crops, compared to previous years (no statistical analysis is implemented for carrots due to the small numbers). Surprisingly (since it contradicts the above values, according to which the implementation year was characterised by lower production), adopters tended to assess more often their potato, and onion yields as **higher** compared to previous years in the final survey, and to do so more than non-adopters. These differences are highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). While these responses are based on the farmers' perception, and may have been affected by their awareness of the potential benefits of the app, they still indicate that they **trust** the app's capacity of delivering yield benefits, which could in turn positively impact their likelihood of using it further.

Table 70: Self-assessed change in yields compared to previous years in Morocco

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Carrots	7	3.0(0.0)	3.4(0.8)	0.000	0.500	0.500		
Onions	159	3.0(1.1)	3.3(0.8)	-0.412	0.630	1.041	17.902	0.000
Potatoes	182	3.0(1.0)	3.4(0.9)	-0.152	0.750	0.902	14.484	0.000

Note: The change in yields was assessed using a 5-point Likert scale, from 5 = “much higher” to 1 = “much lower”.

Figure 47: Box plots of self-assessed change in yields compared to previous years in Morocco

In the final survey, the farmers who had installed the app, were further asked if they thought that the **change in yields** was due to them following the instructions provided by the app. Table 71 and Figure 48 below report their answers by crop. Farmers were very positive concerning the usefulness of the app: 80.8% of the potato growers and 81.5% of the onion growers responded that the change in yields were favoured by the app’s instructions at least “to a certain extent” (carrot growers were less positive, but numbers are small). These proportions are significantly larger than 0.50. While these results suggest that these farmers are likely to keep using the app, possibly generating further and wider benefits in the future, they also highlight that **self-assessments** can be very unreliable, since the numbers in Table 65 had shown a clear decline in production across surveys.

Figure 48: To what extent do you think that the change in yield compared to previous years is due to the fact that you followed the irrigation instructions provided by the application?

Table 71: To what extent do you think that the change in yield compared to previous years is due to the fact that you followed the irrigation instructions provided by the application?

Crop	Adopters (n)	Mean (SD)	P(x > 3)	Statistic	p-value
Carrots	6	3.8(1.5)			
Onions	108	4.5(1.1)	0.815	41.565	0.000
Potatoes	120	4.5(1.2)	0.808	44.408	0.000

Note: The farmers assessed the impact of the app on a 6-point Likert scale, from 1 = "not at all", with 2 = "probably not", until 6 = "to an exceptionally large extent". The farmers who selected "I did not experience any significant change," "Difficult to say," or "I did not follow the instructions" are excluded from the analysis. The statistic is a χ -squared test for the probability that the proportion is larger than 0.5.

Similar to the above analysis about the perceived impact of the app on yields, here we present the results in terms of self-assessed **impact of the app on the quantity of inputs used**. The question was only asked in the final survey to the adopters who had used each specific input, and results for each input separately are reported in Table 72, and plotted in Figure 49 below. The percentage of adopters who reported at least a "partial" impact on input use is smaller than 0.2 for most inputs, apart from family labour (0.26), hired labour (0.30), mechanisation services (0.41), energy (0.43), and, as expected given the goal of the app, water (0.92). All the proportions are significantly lower than 0.5, while "energy" does not differ significantly, and "water" is significantly larger. While these numbers are encouraging, they are based on self-assessment, and the farmers may have provided **biased** responses for social desirability or self-suggestion.

Figure 49: Do you think that following the instructions provided in the application has had an impact on the amount of the inputs used in the last agricultural year?

Table 72: Do you think that following the instructions provided in the application has had an impact on the amount of the inputs used in the last agricultural year?

Input	Adopters (n)	Mean (SD)	P(x < 3)	Statistic	p-value
Seeds	157	3.1(0.7)	0.200	53.91	0.000
Seedlings	45	3.0(0.3)	0.040	35.56	0.000
Chemical fertilisers	150	3.0(0.6)	0.150	73.50	0.000
Organic fertilisers	147	3.0(0.6)	0.150	70.78	0.000
Phytosanitary treatments	146	3.1(0.6)	0.100	90.58	0.000
Weed killer	146	3.1(0.6)	0.110	87.46	0.000
Energy	139	2.6(0.7)	0.430	2.33	0.130
Water	157	1.9(0.6)	0.920	107.64	0.000
Mechanisation services	146	2.6(0.7)	0.410	4.28	0.040
Hired labour	148	2.8(0.8)	0.300	21.95	0.000
Family labour	140	2.7(0.6)	0.260	30.18	0.000

Note: The farmers assessed the impact of the app on a 6-point Likert scale (for the levels see note to Table 71). The statistic is a χ -squared test for the probability that the proportion is larger than 0.5.

Finally, to broaden our perspective to the overall **financial conditions** of the farming household, but also as a robustness check (since the farm expenses and sales above were calculated by us, using the figures for each specific crop and input), here we present some figure on farmers' **self-declared expenses** and **incomes**, with a focus on those which might have been affected by the use of the app. The DID analysis is reported in Table 73, while the box plots are shown in Figure 50 below. Differently from what we expected based on the dynamics usually observed in developing countries, where survey respondents tend to underreport incomes and overreport expenses, in our sample the earnings from farm sales are higher than the expenses in both the initial and final surveys. Both figures tend to increase more among adopters, but only the change in the value of sales is significantly larger among this group. Neither farm nor energy expenses register a significant difference in the change between the two groups. This result contradicts the previous result that the implementation year was characterised by lower production and sales, and **further analyses** would be required to determine if the increase in aggregate farm sales is driven by the app.

Table 73: Monthly household earnings and expenses in Morocco

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Farm expenses (1,000 MAD)	234	5.2(2.8)	9.2(7.8)	3.151	4.377	1.226	1.122	0.263
Energy expenses (MAD)	210	203.2(243.8)	264.8(192.2)	45.779	70.802	25.023	0.390	0.532
Total farm sales (1,000 MAD)	225	7.9(4.4)	12.3(8.7)	2.913	5.295	2.383	2.149	0.033

Figure 50: Box plots of monthly household expenses and earnings in Morocco

To conclude the overview of impact in Morocco, the farmers seem to have perceived some benefits in terms of **yields**, which nevertheless could only be verified for onions (smaller drop compared to non-adopters). Additionally, we registered a positive impact on input use, in terms of lower **water and energy** needs. Nevertheless, these benefits were not larger enough to trigger wider **benefits** (e.g., a reduction in irrigation hours, or significant higher yields at parity of input use, or lower input requirements to achieve the same yields) that could result in higher income for the farming households. While we detected higher incomes from farm sales, our analysis is too preliminary to univocally associate this change to the use of the app; and the aggregate **sales value** does not match our calculations based on individual crop production and input use. Nevertheless, the app is meant to generate **environmental benefits** in terms of reduced water stress that go beyond the immediate wellbeing of the farming household involved, and that could not be assessed here.

4.2. Tanzania: New nutrient-rich bean varieties

In **Tanzania**, the sample size for the impact analysis, reported in Table 1 in Section 1.2, consists of **267** farmers, of which 195 adopters (73.0%) and 72 non-adopters. In this country, the treatment groups for the analysis of adoption had quite different sizes, thus the largest number of adopters (73, 37.4%) belong to T2, which was initially the largest group, followed by T3 (63, 32.3%), and by T1 (59, 30.3%). In Tanzania we use a single definition of adoption, consisting of **having grown** at least one of the two new bean varieties (NUA-660, or Mashamba PYT-4) during the implementation year. As shown in the Section 3.2, the farmers' attitude and behaviours towards the two varieties did not differ significantly, besides the fact that some farmers were not provided with seeds of Mashamba PYT-4 due to limited availability (but these farmers were randomly selected). Given exchanges of seeds between farmers, and other unassessed dynamics during the implementation year, 192 farmers (98.5% of the adopters) grew NUA-660, and 191 (97.9%) grew Mashamba PYT-4. Hence, we will not create separate groups of adopters, but report variety-specific figures when relevant, e.g., yields and selling prices.

Following the structure of the analysis already adopted for Morocco, our first focus is on **production** variables, in this case only referred to **beans** (any varieties). The DID analysis is reported in Table 74, while box plots are shown in Figure 51. Noteworthy, the declared production levels are much lower in the final survey on average, especially among producers: between the two surveys, adopters experience a **decrease** in the quantity produced which is 129 kg larger than among non-adopters, an associated decrease in the value of production 195,564 TZS larger, a decrease in the quantity sold 97 kg larger, and an associated decrease in the value of sales 128,914 TZS larger – to only list the difference-in-differences that are statistically significant. The declines happen without a corresponding larger decrease in the land area devoted to beans. Such figures are **surprising**, and call for further research. While the farming season during the implementation period may have been less successful due to climatic and other conditions, it is not clear why these conditions would have affected adopters comparatively more. We could hypothesize that adopters did not feel the need to declare their production from varieties different from the new ones, which could have resulted in lower aggregate production and sales figures. Unfortunately, this cannot be verified ex-post. In turn, if considering the land area devoted to the single **varieties** and the farmers who grew the same variety in both years, we see no significant changes between the two surveys (the new bean varieties are omitted because they were not available at the moment of the baseline survey).

Table 74: Farm production variables in Tanzania

Crop	Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
All varieties	land (hectares)	256	1.2(0.6)	0.8(0.6)	-0.283	-0.396	-0.114	-1.192	0.235
	quantity produced (kg)	260	276.6(237.7)	165.8(159)	-16.279	-145.545	-129.267	-4.015	0.000
	produce value (1,000 TZS)	257	486.9(431.9)	351.9(343.5)	8.108	-187.456	-195.564	-3.214	0.002
	sales quantity (kg)	260	225.5(211.4)	124.6(136.6)	-30.014	-127.503	-97.489	-3.188	0.002
	sales value (1,000 TZS)	256	391.2(373.3)	263.7(294.5)	-33.841	-162.755	-128.914	-2.292	0.023
	self-consumption (kg)	259	1.0(0)	24.3(29.9)	24.971	22.767	-2.203	-0.53	0.597
Land area by variety	Soya nyekundu	150	0.7(0.7)	0.7(0.6)	0.173	-0.023	-0.195	-1.277	0.206
	Soya nyeupe	101	0.5(0.7)	0.3(0.5)	-0.119	-0.174	-0.055	-0.255	0.800
	Goroli nyekundu	49	0.7(0.7)	0.4(0.5)	-0.533	-0.114	0.419	1.351	0.188
	Njano ndefu	34	0.7(0.6)	0.4(0.4)	-0.656	-0.212	0.445	1.696	0.105
	Njano goroli	56	0.7(0.8)	0.3(0.5)	-0.071	-0.417	-0.346	-1.354	0.188
Not specified	55	1.1(0.4)	0.0(0.0)	-1.173	-1.030	0.143	0.823	0.423	

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Figure 51: Box plots of farm production variables in Tanzania

Although the new bean varieties were not available at the moment of the initial survey, we can still compare their **performance** to the performance of the standard varieties in the final survey. Table 75 reports the results of this exercise; the box plots are provided in Figure 52. The average **yields** per hectare of the new varieties are significantly lower than the standard varieties (139 kg for NUA-660 and 133 kg for Mashamba PYT-4, against 223 kg for the standard varieties, pulled together). In turn, the **seed rate** is significantly smaller – less than half, although this might be due to the trial nature of the exercise – and the **maturation time** shorter by around two days on average. Those who sold some of their produce, were able to charge a lower **price** for NUA-660 and a higher one for Mashamba PYT-4, which could be a confirmation of the better appearance of the latter, which we had already hypothesised based on the results in terms of adoption, and family consumption. The share of **produce lost** was significantly higher for the new varieties, although negligible. This could be due to the limited experience of the farmers with these varieties, leading to crop failures.

Table 75: Performance of the new bean varieties compared to the standard varieties in Tanzania

Variable	Mean (SD) – Standard varieties	Mean (SD) – NUA-660	Statistic NUA-660 vs Standard	p-value	Mean (SD) – Mashamba PYT-4	Statistic Mashamba vs Standard	p-value
Yield (kg / ha)	222.8(247.5)	139.0(182.5)	39.175	0.000	132.5(159.4)	40.398	0.000
Seed rate (kg / ha)	28.0(28.7)	12.8(8.9)	114.583	0.000	12.9(9.1)	113.309	0.000
Maturation time (days)	87.2(6.3)	85.7(8.2)	5.784	0.016	85.7(8.1)	4.113	0.043
Selling price (TZS/kg)	2,089.2(195.4)	2,029.0(328.1)	397.14	0.000	2,345.3(260.8)	409.66	0.000
Crop losses (share of production)	0.01(0.04)	0.01(0.08)	11.488	0.001	0.01(0.08)	13.354	0.000

Notes: The p-values in this table refer to Kruskal-Wallis rank sum tests. Some enumerators misreported the land areas, writing 0.125 ha instead of 0.0125 ha for the surface devoted to the new beans: these data entry errors were detected during the analysis, and adjusted before running statistical tests.

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Figure 52: Box plots illustrating the performance of the new bean varieties compared to the standard varieties in Tanzania

The DID analysis of **farm input cost and quantities** is provided in Table 76, with the box plots in Figure 53. While we did not make any assumption in terms of input requirements to grow the new bean varieties compared to the standard ones, we can hypothesise that if they were grown on top of the standard varieties, the scale effect may have resulted in larger values among the adopters. Instead, most of the differences in the differences are not statistically significant. The only exception is represented by the quantity and cost of **seeds**, which decrease for all farmers on average, but relatively less among adopters: 6.5 kg and 241,000 TZS. In a context of decrease in the scale of production, the adoption of the new varieties may have mitigated this dynamic. Additionally, the adopters see a drop in the demand of mechanisation services, opposite to an increase among non-adopters – a finding that we can hardly attribute to growing the new bean varieties.

Table 76: Farm input variables in Tanzania

Variable	Input	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Input costs (1,000 TZS)	Seeds	261	610.1(492.3)	410.9(416.2)	-22.182	-264.109	-241.927	-3.206	0.002
	Chemical fertilisers	158	63.8(88.2)	53.6(44.4)	5.814	-16.130	-21.944	-1.332	0.186
	Insecticides	221	105.9(91.4)	68.5(51.4)	-40.410	-36.281	4.129	0.271	0.787
	Fungicides	216	87.9(68.5)	67.2(56.4)	-24.433	-19.327	5.106	0.416	0.678
	Weed killer	45	129.4(141)	67.2(95.9)	-37.800	-69.229	-31.429	-0.566	0.578
	Mechanisation services	110	299.3(430.6)	180.5(319.9)	-130.417	-115.523	14.893	0.115	0.909
	Hired labour	177	367.7(402.4)	263.9(290)	-25.833	-132.868	-107.035	-1.468	0.145
	Organic fertiliser	31	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	0.000	0.000	0.000		
	Other	31	43.9(50.1)	40(55.3)	-38.571	6.250	44.821	1.281	0.223
Input quantity (kg or days)	Seeds	261	36.8(20.5)	20.8(18)	-11.168	-17.707	-6.539	-2.244	0.026
	Chemical fertilisers	43	27.3(48.9)	28.1(39.1)	-6.667	2.735	9.402	0.370	0.718
	Insecticides	214	0.6(0.6)	0.3(0.2)	-0.377	-0.377	0.000	0.003	0.998
	Fungicides	45	0.8(0.9)	0.6(0.9)	0.140	-0.227	-0.367	-0.819	0.423
	Weed killer	203	0.7(0.7)	0.1(0.1)	-0.514	-0.534	-0.020	-0.174	0.862
	Mechanisation services	117	2.4(2.5)	2.3(3.1)	1.917	-0.591	-2.508	-2.170	0.038
	Hired labour	173	2.1(1.9)	2(1.8)	0.043	-0.213	-0.256	-0.545	0.587
	Organic fertiliser	132	0.5(0.8)	0.8(0.6)	0.238	0.214	-0.024	-0.101	0.920
	Other	24	0.7(0.9)	0.5(0.7)	-0.417	-0.172	0.244	0.376	0.716
Total input cost (1,000 TZS)		253	122.1(94.3)	83.0(78.5)	-13.814	-48.426	-34.612	-2.846	0.005

In Table 76 above, we include only the farmers who reported each input twice, both in the baseline and in the final survey. If we counted the farmers who reported each input at least once, the most used input are seeds (100% of the respondents), followed by insecticide and fungicide (87% and 86% respectively), hired labour (69%), chemical fertilisers (63%), mechanisation services (45%), and, at a certain distance, organic fertiliser (19%), weed killer (17%), and “other” (13%).

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Figure 53: Box plots of farm input variables in Tanzania

The difference between the value of production and the total cost of farm inputs yields the **profit** from growing beans. The DID analysis of profits is provided in Table 77 below, while the box plots are provided in Figure 54. As expected given the relatively large decrease in the value of production among adopters between the baseline and final surveys, we register a significantly larger decrease in farm profit among this group. More precisely, while average profits are positive in both surveys, adopters experience an average drop of 131,757 TZS between the two surveys, which considering the increase experienced by non-adopters, results in a difference-in-differences of 156,758 TZS. Again, we cannot univocally attribute this figure to the new varieties, highlighting a need for further research and larger-scale on-farm trials.

Table 77: Farm profit (1,000 TZS) from beans in Tanzania

Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
258	351.2(384.3)	261.4(304.2)	25.001	-131.757	-156.758	-2.783	0.006

Figure 54: Box plots of farm profit in Tanzania

In the final survey, farmers were asked to assess if in the last season, the yield per hectare of the varieties grown had been higher, similar to, or lower than in the previous seasons. Their responses by variety are plotted in Figure 55 (all the standard varieties were considered jointly), and further analysed in Table 78 below. The number of farmers who declared to have difficulties in comparing the yields was higher for the new varieties, probably due to their more limited experience and the small quantity of seeds provided. Overall, there was no significant trend toward positive (“higher”), or negative (“lower”) assessments; nevertheless, the proportion of farmers who declared “higher” yields was significantly larger for both new varieties compared to the standard ones, primarily for NUA-660 (49.0% of those who expressed a judgement). While this assessment is probably biased for social desirability and self-suggestion, it is still a positive sign for the new varieties and SUA.

Figure 55: How was the yield per hectare of the following varieties during this farming seasons, compared to the average of all varieties in previous seasons?

Table 78: How was the yield per hectare of the following varieties during this year's farming seasons, compared to the average for all varieties in previous seasons?

Input	Adopters (n)	Mean (SD)	P(x > 3)	Statistic ¹	p-value ¹	Statistic ²	p-value ²
NUA-660	151	3.1(1.2)	49.0% (74)	1.238	0.109	5.040	0.000
Mashamba PYT-4	153	3.1(1.2)	43.1% (66)	0.966	0.168	3.853	0.000
Standard	317	2.8(1.7)	25.6% (81)	-3.571	1.000		

Notes: The farmers were asked to assess the yields on a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 = “much lower” to 5 = “much larger” (0 = “difficult to say” and 99 = “I have never grown beans before” were excluded). ¹ t-test on whether the responses are significantly higher than 3 = “about the same”. ² t-test on whether the proportion of those responding “higher” or “much higher” are larger compared to the standard variety.

However, the change in yields could be due to reasons other than the variety. Hence, the farmers who had grown either of the new varieties were asked if they believed that the **change in yields** was due to the new varieties, regardless of whether the yields were higher or lower than in previous years. Their responses are plotted in Figure 56 below: most farmers thought that the new varieties

had impacted yields, the median response being “to a certain extent”. After removing the farmers who had not perceived any changes, or who could not say, the proportion of farmers who thought that the new varieties had had at least “partial” impact is 85.0%, which is significantly different from 0.5 based on a test of difference of proportions ($\chi^2 = 70.78, p < 0.001$).

Figure 56: To what extent do you think that the change in yield is due to the new varieties?

The following step in the self-assessment consisted in asking farmers if they thought that the new varieties had **impacted** the **quantity of inputs** used. Their responses are reported, and analysed in Table 79, and plotted in Figure 57 below. Like in the question about yields, a large percentage of farmers stated that they could not say with certainty. Among those who expressed a judgement, a large majority (77.0% across all the inputs) declared that they had not detected any change. The percentages of those who declared a positive outcome (“decrease”) is below 20% for most inputs, and in no case the assessment differs significantly from “no change” (except for the residual category “other”, which is a composite aggregate). Hence, we can conclude that our farmers did not perceive any significant benefits of the new varieties in terms of input requirements.

Figure 57: How do you think the new varieties have impacted the quantity of inputs used?

Table 79: Farmer's opinion on how the new varieties have impacted the quantity of inputs used

Input	Adopters (n)	Mean (SD)	P(x > 3)	Statistic	p-value
Seeds	169	3.1(0.9)	14.8% (25)	0.905	0.817
Chemical fertilisers	93	3.1(0.6)	6.5% (6)	1.631	0.947
Organic fertilisers	46	3.2(0.6)	6.5% (3)	1.942	0.971
Insecticide	133	3.1(0.6)	7.5% (10)	1.614	0.946
Fungicide	131	3.1(0.6)	6.1% (8)	2.589	0.995
Weed killer	26	3.0(0.8)	15.4% (4)	-0.238	0.407
Mechanisation services	53	3.1(0.5)	5.7% (3)	1.158	0.874
Hired labour	93	3.0(0.2)	2.2% (2)	0.000	0.500
Other	17	2.9(0.3)	11.8% (2)	-1.461	0.082

Notes: The farmers were asked to assess the impact on a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 = "Large decrease" to 5 = "Large increase" (0 = "difficult to say" and 99 = "I have never used that input" were excluded). The p-values refer to a t-test on whether the responses are significantly lower than 3 = "no change".

We have seen that some farmers sold part of their production of the new bean varieties. Here, we focus on the **selling channels**, that farmers were asked to select out of nine options. Overall, nine farmers sold NUA-660 (5.3% of those with a non-zero production), while 13 sold Mashamba PYT-4 (7.6%), and 227 (73.0%) sold the standard varieties. The number of selling channels was always one for the new varieties and for 214 (94.3%) of the sellers of the standard varieties, while nine of the latter had used two channels, and four three channels. As shown in Table 80 below, the main selling strategy overall was via direct sales in the village market (69.2% for the standard varieties), but this was less frequently used for the new varieties, for which **home sales** were more common, given the limited quantities – a difference that is statistically significant for Mashamba PYT-4.

Table 80: Percentage of farmers using each selling channel, by bean variety

Selling channel	Standard	NUA-660	p-value	Mashamba PYT-4	p-value
Village market (direct)	69.2	44.4	0.119	38.5	0.022
Home sales	21.6	33.3	0.407	46.2	0.041
Intermediator	15.4	22.2	0.584	15.4	0.997
City market (direct)	0.0	0.00	0.843	0.0	0.811
Food company	0.0	0.00	0.843	0.0	0.811
Acquaintances, friends, family	0.0	0.00	0.843	0.0	0.811

Notes: Each farmer who was selling beans could select as many channels as relevant for each variety, between nine.

In this final part of the impact analysis, we focus on the **financial situation** of the farming household, as well as on **healthiness** outcomes and use of **fuel for cooking** – two aspects which were targeted by the bean varieties, thanks to their richness in zinc and iron, and shorter cooking time. The new bean varieties can only impact farm costs and the value of sales, not other income types: these aggregates are reported in Table 81 below, with the box plots presented in Figure 58. In line with the previous results, we register a large decrease in both indicators between the baseline and the final surveys, the decrease being significantly larger on average among adopters (42,336 TZS the expenses, and 262,004 TZS the value of sales). This is a very large difference which requires further investigation.

Table 81: Monthly farm earnings and expenses in Tanzania

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Farm expenses (1,000 TZS)	251	201.6(169.6)	14.0(12.1)	-156.747	-199.083	-42.336	-1.880	0.062
Total farm sales (1,000 TZS)	251	693.6(604.5)	55.7(48.4)	-443.709	-705.713	-262.004	-4.046	0.000

Figure 58: Box plots of monthly farm earnings and expenses in Tanzania

The implementation period was too short for the beans to generate visible benefits for the **health** of household members, if consumed. Nevertheless, we included in the baseline and final surveys a set of questions on this matter to be able to implement a DID analysis. The results are reported in Table 82 and illustrated through box plots in Figure 59. As expected, the frequency of **consuming beans** did not change significantly because of the new varieties, being between once a week and a few times per week on average. The number of **nutrition-related diseases** experienced by the household decreased from 1.2 to 0.7, but this variation is not statistically significant, and does not differ between adopters and non-adopters. Finally, the self-assessed health conditions did not differ either, the average being slightly below “good” in both occurrences, and among both groups.

Table 82: Bean consumption and health-related variables in Tanzania

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Frequency of consuming beans	267	4.9(0.6)	4.8(0.8)	-0.150	-0.070	0.080	0.620	0.430
Nutrition-related diseases (count)	267	1.2(1.3)	0.7(0.9)	-0.450	-0.570	-0.120	0.060	0.814
Self-assessed health conditions	267	3.8(0.7)	3.9(0.5)	0.100	0.110	0.010	0.060	0.806

Notes: The frequency of consuming beans was assessed on a 7-point Likert scale, from 0 = “never” to 6 = “every day”. The number of nutrition-related diseases assessed was nine (anaemia, scurvy, night blindness, constipation, goitre, diabetes, hypertension, peptic ulcer, and “other”): farmers had to indicate if anyone in their household had experienced them during the last year. The health conditions of household members were assessed on a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 = “very bad” to 5 = “very good”.

Figure 59: Box plots of bean consumption and health-related variables in Tanzania

Despite the short-term demonstration and the limited quantity of beans available to the farmers, in the final survey, those who had consumed the new varieties were asked if they thought that the fact of consuming them had **impacted their health**, either positively or negatively. Only 32 farmers responded to this question, given the small number who had consumed the varieties, and among the 29 who provided an assessment, 19 (65.5%) stated that they had a “positive” or “very positive” impact (significantly different from 0.5, $z = 1.67$, $p < 0.095$). While this result is likely to be due to **self-suggestion**, it is still a positive outcome for the new variety and a sign of trust towards SUA.

Figure 60: Do you think that consuming the new bean varieties has impacted your health?

Finally, we asked the farmers if the quantity of **fuel used for cooking** had changed compared to the previous years. Our hypothesis is that the consumption of the new bean varieties had resulted in lower fuel use, compared to a situation where other varieties requiring longer cooking time were mostly consumed. However, we saw already in Section 3.2 that only a small proportion of farmers had consumed the beans; additionally, the available quantity was limited, at least at the beginning of the growing season. Thus, 73.0% of the farmers stated that they had experienced no difference, and only 13.9% that they had experienced a reduction, with no significant difference between non-adopters and adopter, as shown in the bar graphs in Figure 61 and tested statistically in Table 83.

Figure 61: Self-assessed change in fuel consumption, by adoption

Table 83: Results of differences in means for self-assessed change in fuel consumption

Adopters (n)	Non-adopters (n)	Proportion adopters	Proportion non-adopters	Statistic	p-value
191	70	0.152	0.114	0.768	0.443

Note: We assess the proportion of people who assessed their fuel consumption as “more” or “much more” compared to the previous year.

To conclude the overview of the impact analysis in Tanzania, we must recognise that the demonstration period was **too short**, and the **quantity** of bean seeds provided **too small** to register any significant impact on farm performance and household well-being, especially on health conditions, which would require a more significant shift in dietary patterns to be affected. Additionally, we saw a significant **decline in farm production** and the resulting income among adopters, compared to non-adopters, for which we are unable to provide a reasonable explanation. The enumerators may have failed to explain the need of providing information about all the bean varieties grown, besides the new ones. However, this is only a hypothesis that we cannot verify ex-post. Despite the above

shortcomings, the new varieties are characterised by a significantly **lower seed rate** and **shorter maturation time**, which can be mentioned as additional advantages besides the richness in zinc and iron, and their shorter cooking time. Additionally, despite the small quantity of seeds received, some farmers were able to sell part of their production, and especially for **Mashamba PYT-4**, they were able to charge on average higher prices compared to standard varieties. Therefore, now that the new varieties have been introduced in the Mvomero Food Hub, smallholder farmers can further multiply them, possibly start consuming them in larger quantities, and turn them into an additional source of farm income for their households.

4.3. Uganda: Integrated fish-vegetable farming

The sample size for the impact analysis in **Uganda**, reported in Table 1 in Section 1.2, is smaller compared to the other countries. This is mostly due to the large **investment** required to install the innovation, which resulted in a lower adoption rate, as expected. Depending on the definition of “adoption” used, this sample consists of **147** farmers of which 43 adopters (29.3%), or **136** farmers of which 32 adopters (21.8%), while the number of non-adopters remains the same (104). The first definition includes among the adopters those who had a system similar to the one proposed already installed in their farm before the baseline training but upgraded it in line with the instructions provided by NARO (12 across the T1, T2, and T3 groups). The second definition excludes them. The fish farmers who had a similar system already installed, are also excluded from the group of non-adopters for this analysis. To avoid reducing the sample size further, in this section we rely on the first (broader) definition of “adoption.” Therefore, the number of adopters is 43, of which the largest number (19, 44%) come from the T3 group, followed by T1 (14, 33%), and finally T1 (10, 23%). It is worth noting that participants were recruited for being fish farmers, and not necessarily engaged in crop farming. However, the adopters had to start growing vegetables, if not already doing this.

Table 84: Farm production variables (crop and fish) in Uganda

Crop or species	Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Crops (total)	land (ha)	138	0.1(0.2)	0.3(0.3)	0.134	0.129	-0.005	-0.098	0.922
	production value (1,000 UGX)	137	741.9(1,078.4)	584.3(838.8)	156.026	161.729	5.703	0.021	0.984
	sales value (1,000 UGX)	130	455.5(638.1)	355.8(566.1)	102.97	91.943	-11.027	-0.062	0.951
Fish (total)	production value (1,000 UGX)	123	3,240.1(4,658.0)	2,056(2,655.8)	699.739	2,505.271	1,805.53	1.586	0.119
	sales value (1,000 UGX)	122	1,794.1(2,269.9)	2,645.5(3,723.8)	331.901	2,252.371	1,920.47	1.951	0.057
Catfish	quantity produced (kg)	121	140.0(235)	161.1(308.4)	-20.59	128.03	148.62	1.773	0.183
	production value (1,000 UGX)	122	785.9(1,356.7)	1,110.5(2,143.6)	202.22	654.6	452.38	0.489	0.484
	quantity sold (kg)	122	650.6(1,129.0)	1,018.5(2,018.0)	182.59	847.42	664.83	1.192	0.275
	sales value (1,000 UGX)	97	1,318.5(2,028.0)	2,828.6(4,827.2)	984.42	3,201.42	2,217.00	2.864	0.091
	yield (kg/sq. m.)	53	1.5(1.7)	1.7(1.9)	0.099	0.380	0.281	0.390	0.698
Tilapia	quantity produced (kg)	123	101.8(175.1)	212(388)	70.58	209.91	139.33	0.412	0.521
	production value (1,000 UGX)	121	693(1,281.8)	1,117.5(2,021.5)	252.52	883.28	630.76	0.064	0.800
	quantity sold (kg)	118	582.7(1,123.4)	860.4(1,592.9)	135.79	658.96	523.17	0.156	0.693
	sales value (1,000 UGX)	91	1,530.7(2,258.8)	2,103.1(3,059.5)	484.99	725.93	240.94	0.016	0.898
	yield (kg/sq. m.)	47	2.2(2.5)	1.7(1.6)	-0.516	-0.695	-0.179	-0.196	0.847

Like in other countries, we first focus on **production** variables, which in this case refer to both fish and crop farming. As reported in Table 84 and Figure 62, in most instances there is no significant difference in the differences between the baseline and final surveys. Adopters seem to experience an increase in the value of their overall fish production (by 2,505,271 UGX on average, 1,805,532

UGX more than non-adopters), as well as their overall **fish sales** (by 2,252,371 UGX on average, 1,920,470 UGX more than non-adopters), with the latter difference being statistically significant. The values of the specific production indicators for catfish and tilapia separately seem favourable for adopters: they increase their production and sales, and more than non-adopters; nevertheless, only the value of sales for catfish results in a (marginally) significant and positive DID. Noteworthy, we do not detect any significant improvement in **crop** production indicators among adopters relative to non-adopters, in spite of vegetable production being the focus of the Ugandan innovation (we only report aggregated values because crop diversity is very high, thus the number of farmers growing the same crop in both years is very small). This lack of visible improvement in vegetable farming might be due to the short duration of the demonstration, which did not allow enough time for adopters to make the most of their activity.

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Figure 62: Box plots of farm production variables (crop and fish) in Uganda

While the high level of crop diversity did not allow to compare the production of specific vegetables across the two surveys, it is still worth identifying the most common crops. Farmers could indicate up to three **vegetables**. In the baseline survey, the vegetable listed most often is the eggplant (70 farmers, 47.6% of the sample), followed by amaranth (39, 26.5%), tomato (36, 24.5%), cabbage (34, 23.1%), beans (15, 10.2%), and nakati (14, 9.5%), while others appeared less than ten times. In the final survey, the most common was again the eggplant (59, 40.1%), followed by beans (49, 33.3%), cabbage (39, 26.5%), amaranth (36, 24.5%), tomato (32, 21.8%), sukuma (24, 16.3%), and nakati (22, 15.0%). Except for sukuma, all the vegetables listed appear in both surveys. However, Only eggplant (23), amaranth (15), and cabbage (13) see more than ten farmers (the same) growing them in both surveys. Concerning instead the **fish species**, tilapia and catfish dominate, with 89 farmers (60.5%) growing tilapia in the baseline survey and 86 (58.5%) in the final one, and 75 farmers (51.0%) growing catfish in the baseline survey and 89 (60.5%) in the final one. There are 112 occurrences of farmers growing the same species in both surveys (60 tilapia, and 52 catfish), but the largest increase is seen in the latter, proportionally more among adopters.

Table 85: Farm input variables (crop and fish) in Uganda

Variable	Input	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Crop inputs (1,000 UGX)	Chemical fertilisers	81	39.3(64.8)	81.9(135.4)	86.66	28.24	58.42	1.286	0.257
	Organic fertiliser	73	2.6(7.8)	12.7(31.8)	17.50	7.23	10.27	6.538	0.011
	Weed killer	63	27.4(43.2)	63.4(77.8)	12.46	45.46	-33.00	1.482	0.223
Crop input quantity (kg)	Chemical fertilisers	67	4.1(8.5)	6.2(11.6)	4.30	1.28	3.02	0.096	0.756
	Organic fertiliser	90	82.7(151.9)	595.4(897.2)	613.05	467.34	145.71	0.030	0.862
	Weed killer	61	1.2(1.8)	3.8(5.1)	1.82	2.90	-1.08	0.242	0.623
Total crop inputs (1,000 UGX)		133	381.6(486.8)	691.9(893.5)	620.91	207.83	413.08	2.45	0.117
Fish inputs (1,000 UGX)	Feed	130	493.9(621.8)	861.8(1,088.9)	512.45	320.62	191.83	0.044	0.833
Fish input quantity (kg)	Feed	128	214.7(294.6)	261.8(363.5)	164.27	3.07	161.20	2.900	0.089
	Energy	21	3.6(6.7)	7.2(9.2)	4.54	2.13	2.41	0.191	0.662
	Water	4	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.1)	0.07	0.00	0.07		
Total fish inputs (1,000 UGX)		132	969.6(1,086.9)	1,620.1(1,964.4)	525.833	1,009.75	483.91	1.168	0.248

Table 85 above, and Figure 63 below present the DID analysis for **fish and crop farming inputs**. Overall, the cost of inputs increases more among adopters, by 413,080 UGX crop inputs, and by 483,910 UGX fish inputs. This is expected given that the innovation may have triggered larger initial needs in terms of variable inputs as well as an increase in the scale of production, however the difference in the differences is not significant. Looking at the quantity and cost of specific inputs

(only those with a larger enough number of observations in both the initial and final surveys are reported), we detect, among adopters, a significantly larger increase in the cost of organic fertilisers, by 10,270 UGX, and a significant larger increase in the quantity of fish feed, by 161,200 UGX. The latter was expected, given the potentially larger production scale and the need to demonstrate good quality of production, at least in the T3 group; while the former was not expected given that irrigating the vegetables with aquaculture water should have decreased the need for additional fertilisation, but probably the scale effect prevailed, at least in the initial production cycles.

Figure 63: Box plots of farm input variables (crop and fish) in Uganda

Like for other countries, after having discussed production and inputs separately, we illustrate the results in terms of **farm profit**, obtained as the difference between the value of production and the total cost of inputs. In Table 86, and Figure 63 below, we report the DID results for **crop and fish** farming separately as well as overall farm profit (i.e., the sum of these two). Adopters experience a larger increase in crop farm profit by 593,493 UGX, fish farm profit by 364,147 UGX, and overall, by 1,409,275 UGX. However, none of these differences in the differences is statistically significant.

Table 86: Profit (1,000 UGX) from fish farming, crop farming, and overall, in Uganda

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Crop farming	134	1,252.2(2,223.1)	1,387.7(2,882.6)	-32.720	560.772	593.493	0.775	0.442
Fish farming	127	744.3(1971.1)	872.8(2,145.3)	31.075	395.222	364.147	0.602	0.550
Total	125	1,422.6(3,682.6)	2,459.2(5,254.7)	642.019	2,051.294	1,409.275	1.022	0.312

Figure 64: Box plots of profit from fish farming, crop farming, and overall, in Uganda

As part of the **self-assessment of change**, adopters were asked whether they thought that using aquaculture water via the system had caused an increase in **yields**. Only those adopters who had already started irrigating their vegetables responded to this question, thus the numbers are small. Their responses are shown in Figure 65, and suggest that the impact was strongly positive, since 22 out of 36 respondents (72.2%) declared that the innovation had increased their yields to a large or exceptionally large extent, and only one that probably there had been no impact. The share of respondents declaring a positive impact is significantly larger than 0.5 ($z = 5.67, p < 0.001$).

Figure 65: To what extent do you think that using aquaculture water via the integrated system has caused an increase in yields? (Count of responses)

Afterwards, all the farmers who had used each single crop input were asked if they had perceived a change in the required **quantity**. We asked this question only with respect to the **inputs** used to grow **crops**, because the system was conceived specifically for allowing irrigation and fertilisation of vegetables by means of aquaculture water. We thus expected a reduction in the need of water, chemical fertilisers, and organic fertilisers. However, we did not exclude a scale effects, potentially resulting in an increase in input demand overall. Farmers’ responses are plotted in Figure 66, and analysed in Table 87, where we test the difference between adopters and non-adopters. First, the bar graphs suggest that a large share of farmers did not observe any changes, but in most cases, with the exceptions of mechanisation services and to a lesser extent, seeds, and organic fertilisers, 50% or more of those who expressed an assessment, stated that they had used larger quantities. The percentage of farmers declaring a reduction in input requirements is small, less than 20% on average across all the types of inputs, and does not differ significantly between non-adopters and adopters, except for chemical fertilisers (23.4% of the non-adopters declared to have experienced a reduction, compared to 4.8% of adopters), and fungicides (6.7% vs 35.3%). Equally, the tests in Table 87 suggest that the average assessment does not differ significantly between non-adopters and adopters, regardless of the type of input considered.

Figure 66: Self-assessed change in the quantity of inputs used for crop farming in Uganda

Table 87: Self-assessed change in the quantity of inputs used for crop farming in Uganda

Input	Adopters (n)	Non-adopters (n)	Mean (SD) Adopters	Mean (SD) Non-adopt.	Statistic	p-value
Seeds	40	98	3.1(0.2)	3.3(0.1)	-0.611	0.541
Seedlings	18	56	3.5(0.2)	3.2(0.2)	-0.999	0.318
Chemical fertiliser	21	47	3.7(0.2)	3.3(0.2)	1.148	0.251
Organic fertiliser	37	70	3.4(0.2)	3.2(0.2)	-1.513	0.130
Insecticide	28	67	3.6(0.2)	3.3(0.1)	1.296	0.195
Fungicide	6	17	3.8(0.5)	3.3(0.4)	-0.834	0.404
Weed killers	19	37	3.6(0.3)	3.6(0.2)	-0.571	0.568
Water	18	29	3.4(0.2)	3.8(0.2)	-0.181	0.857
Energy	10	5	3.8(0.3)	3.8(0.6)	-0.519	0.604
Rent	1	15	3.0(.)	3.8(0.2)		
Mechanisation services	4	5	3.0(0.0)	3.2(0.2)		
Other	23	38	3.6(0.2)	3.4(0.1)	-0.846	0.398

Note: The farmers assessed the change in the quantity of inputs used on a 5-level Likert scale from 1 = “much lower” to 5 “much higher”. “Difficult to say” and non-users were omitted. We implement rank tests of the difference in values.

After being asked about changes in input requirements, adopters were asked if they thought that these changes could be **attributed** to the installation of the system. The 16 responses are plotted in Figure 67 below: most farmers (60%) thought that the changes could not be attributed the system, as confirmed by a test of proportions ($\chi^2 = 0.267$, $p = 0.606$). While irrigating vegetables with aquaculture water can reduce the need for fertilisation in the longer-term, the demonstration period was too short to fully appreciate these benefits.

Figure 67: To what extent do you think that the change in input requirements is due to the use of aquaculture water via the system? (Count of responses)

We expected the installation of the system to cause a change in the sources of **water for irrigation** among adopters, as their ponds became relatively more important in this regard. The ranking of sources for irrigation water in the baseline and final surveys is provided in Table 88. We observe a relative increase in the importance of rain (although the rankings are very low compared to the other sources), and a relative decrease in the importance of canals and underground water (wells) among adopters, probably driven by the increase in the importance of **ponds**. The ranking of the latter cannot be compared between the surveys; indeed, they were not an option at the baseline survey, and were only introduced in the final one. The ranking of ponds among adopters and non-adopters is shown in Figure 67 below, while Table 89 reports the results of a *t*-test of the difference in the proportion of farmers who ranked this potential source. As expected, the difference is highly significant, with adopters ranking ponds much more often – probably the few adopters who did not rank them (less than 20%) are using their aquaculture tanks instead.

Table 88: Ranking of sources of irrigation water in Uganda

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) Final	Diff. final – baseline Adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
River	147	0.0(0.2)	0.0(0.2)	-0.020	0.000	-0.02	0.000	1.000
Lake	147	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	0.000	0.000	0.00		
Rain	147	0.0(0.2)	0.1(0.5)	0.300	0.000	0.30	11.058	0.001
Canals	147	0.2(0.7)	0.3(0.8)	-0.210	0.200	-0.41	3.537	0.060
Mains	147	0.0(0.2)	0.2(0.7)	0.160	0.170	-0.01	0.042	0.837
Underground (well)	147	0.3(0.9)	0.2(0.8)	-0.480	0.050	-0.53	7.506	0.006

Notes: Farmers were asked to rank up to 3 sources, 1 being the most important and 3 the least important. To implement the analysis, a value of 3 was assigned to the most important, up to 1 to the least important, and 0 to the sources not ranked. No one ranked “lake.”

Figure 68: Ranking of pond as a source of irrigation water among adopter and non-adopters

Table 89: Ranking of pond as a source of irrigation water among adopters and non-adopters

Adopters (n)	Non-adopters (n)	Proportion adopters	Proportion non-adopters	Statistic	p-value
43	104	0.791	0.385	18.48	0.000

Note: We define a dummy variables that takes value 1 if pond is the first ranked source of irrigation, 0 otherwise.

In parallel with the change in the sources of water for irrigation, the installation of the systems was expected to cause a change in the **places to discharge aquaculture water**, with **land** becoming relatively more prominent. In this case, the option of discharging on land was already provided in the baseline survey, since not all farmers could be expected to have access to water bodies near their ponds or tanks. Table 90 below provides the DID results for the comparison of places where to discharge aquaculture water as well as for the frequency of water discharge. As expected, **land** becomes significantly more important for adopters compared to non-adopters, while canals see a marginally significant movement in the opposite direction. Adopters also see a significantly larger increase in the **frequency of discharging water** compared to non-adopters, suggesting that they have started doing regular use of the innovation for irrigating their vegetables (see Figure 69 too).

Table 90: Ranking of places for discharging water and discharge frequency in Uganda

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopt.	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
River	147	0.2(0.7)	0.1(0.5)	-0.040	-0.090	-0.050	0.067	0.795
Lake	147	0.0(0.3)	0.1(0.4)	0.010	0.120	0.110	0.874	0.350
Canals	147	1.6(1.5)	2.1(1.3)	0.700	0.160	-0.540	2.773	0.096
Underground (well)	147	0.3(0.9)	0.0(0.2)	-0.260	-0.420	-0.160	0.788	0.375
Land	147	0.6(1.2)	0.9(1.3)	-0.090	1.210	1.300	16.981	0.000
Discharge frequency	147	4.0(2.2)	3.3(2.2)	-1.270	0.630	1.900	11.650	0.001

Notes: Farmers were asked to rank up to 3 discharging places, with 1 being the most important and 3 the least important. To implement the analysis, a value of 3 was assigned to the most important, up to 1 to the least important, and 0 to non-ranked places. The frequency of discharge was assessed on a 6-point Likert scale from “all the time (continuously)” to “less than once a month”. No one ranked “lake.”

Figure 69: Box plots of frequency of discharging aquaculture water

The integration of aquaculture and vegetable farming represents a significant improvement in the farmers' production practices which requires relatively large investment but can also attract further **funding**. Therefore, in Table 91 we test if adopters have experienced a significant larger increase in their capacity to obtain loans or credit for their fish farm (including as match funding for installing the system). In line with our expectations, we detect a significant larger increase in credit provision for adopters compared to non-adopters (the difference in the differences is 142,080 UGX). This is a relevant positive spillover and a sign of commitment of the fish farmers who adopted the system.

Table 91: Means of farm financing (1,000 UGX) in Uganda

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopt.	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Loans received	147	178.9(741.4)	579.3(2793.6)	402.960	394.19	-8.770	0.620	0.430
Credit received	147	78.2(234.4)	121.8(653.8)	2.110	144.19	142.080	2.920	0.088

Like for other countries, also for Uganda we now adopt a broader perspective and verify if adopting the innovation had a positive impact on **household expenses and incomes**. This also serves as a robustness check by comparing these broad aggregates to the figures calculated by integrating the information on specific crops and inputs. Table 92 and Figure 70 below present the results of the DID analysis. First, adopters experience a significantly larger increase in the **expenses** related to **crop farming**, by 100,402 UGX, which is likely due to them starting vegetable farming following the adoption of the innovation. The earnings from crop farming also see relatively larger increase, by 103,742 UGX, but the difference with non-adopters is not statistically significant. Adopters also experience larger increases in the expenses and **earnings** related to **fish farming**, which can be related to improvement in practices favoured by the innovation and, for the T3 groups, the expectation of **monitoring**, as a condition for receiving the 25% payment-by-result. However, only the increase in earnings is significantly larger than among non-adopters, by 189,068 UGX on average. Finally, adopters were also expected to improve their diets, thanks to the availability of vegetables grown with aquaculture water. Here, we only check if their expenses to procure food in the market decrease relatively more than among non-adopters, while this topic is discussed more in-depth in the following. Their **food expenses** decrease relatively more, by 11,088 UGX, but this difference is not statistically significant.

Table 92: Monthly household expenses, earnings, and self-assessed food security in Uganda

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Crop farm expenses	132	58.1(68.0)	88.2 (113.3)	6,543	106.945	100.402	3.531	0.001
Fish farm expenses	132	74.5(74.8)	121.1(158.8)	38.116	74.320	36.204	1.234	0.223
Food expenses	142	204.8(203.8)	155.5(153.5)	-46.127	-57.215	-11.088	-0.238	0.813
Crop farm earnings	138	258.8(294)	374.5(368.5)	87.864	191.606	103.742	1.221	0.227
Fish farm earnings	134	149.7(215.4)	231.6(312.4)	29.630	218.698	189.068	2.488	0.016

Notes: The incomes and expenses are expressed in 1,000 UGX.

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Figure 70: Box plots of monthly household expenses, earnings, and food security in Uganda

As a final step, we focus on **household food consumption** with a view to verifying the impact of the innovation on **dietary diversity**. Because most of these variables refer to vegetables, we also discuss here related **production practices**, namely the count of **vegetables** grown, irrigated, and fertilised. As shown in Table 93 and Figure 71 below, the number of vegetable crops grown does not see a significantly larger increase (nor any other significant difference) among adopters, while the number of crops irrigated grows among adopters and declines among non-adopters, resulting in a statistically significant difference in the differences, as expected. The number of crops fertilised does not yield a significant coefficient. Equally, we do not detect any significant changes in terms of crops consumed, frequency of consumption, or food security (i.e., the capacity of the household to satisfy their food needs). The count of vegetable crops consumed increases in the overall sample, from 11.5 to 12.1, but less among adopters, suggesting that producing at larger scale and for the market does not necessarily result in more dietary diversity. The “frequencies” of consumption and the self-assessed level of food security show better outcomes for adopters, but none of these DID indicators is statistically significant.

Table 93: Farming and consumption practices related to vegetables in Uganda

Variable	Observations	Mean (SD) baseline	Mean (SD) final	Diff. final – baseline Non-adopt.	Diff. final – baseline Adopt.	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value
Number of crops grown	147	6.9(4.6)	6.0(2.9)	-0.690	-1.420	-0.730	0.730	0.393
Number of crops irrigated	138	1.8(1.6)	1.5(1.4)	-0.600	0.470	1.070	10.660	0.001
Number of crops fertilised	145	2.1(2.1)	1.9(1.8)	-0.220	-0.090	0.130	0.010	0.930
Number of crops consumed	147	11.5(2.7)	12.1(2)	0.670	0.480	-0.190	0.060	0.804
Average frequency (first group)	147	3.5(0.5)	3.4(0.5)	-0.103	0.043	0.146	1.246	0.216
Number of crops (second group)	146	18.0(3.6)	19.9(2.6)	1.830	1.880	0.050	0.020	0.883
Capacity of satisfying household food needs	147	1.8(1.0)	1.7(0.8)	-0.140	-0.070	0.070	0.000	0.975

Notes: Farmers were provided with a list of 42 crops (including “other”) among which to select those grown; among those selected as grown, they were asked to select those irrigated and those fertilised. Frequency of consumption (first group) is the average for 16 crops, assessed on a 6-level Likert scale, from 0 = “never” to 5 = “every day”. The crops in the second group were selected from a list of 23 (including “other”) . The capacity of satisfying ones’ household food needs is assessed on a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 = “Yes, more than enough” to 5 = “No, I experienced serious food shortages”.

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Figure 71: Box plots of farming and consumption practices related to vegetables in Uganda

To conclude the overview of the innovation demonstration in Uganda, we must again acknowledge that the period was **too short** to detect a significant impact. Differently from Tanzania, where the farmers received a small quantity of seeds that affected negatively the scale of the potential impact, in Uganda the innovation was **fully implemented** despite its costs and complexity, and group-T3 farmers were also audited on an individual basis to verify that they had really installed it,¹¹ and that they were adopting good aquaculture and vegetable farming practices. Additionally, NARO defined “adoption” strictly, as laying pipes to link the ponds and/or tanks with the plots. For these reasons, the number of adopters was smaller than in other countries.

¹¹ While the results of the audit are not reported for confidentiality and conciseness, the exclusion of around half of the farmers who had received an upfront payment from the payment-by-result and hence for the group of adopters, ensure that this latter group is well defined and different from the baseline.

Despite the above challenges we observed significant changes in **water discharge** and **irrigation practices** (use of pond water, larger number of irrigated crops, etc.) among adopters, which prove that the system is fully in place and running. We also detect some important spillovers, such as an increase in access to agricultural **credit**, which could result in longer-term financial sustainability and consolidation of the integrated farms “created” by the project. The quantity and value of vegetable production did not change significantly compared to the baseline survey, probably because the demonstration has started recently, and farmers did not have enough time to realise the gains of this new (for some of them) activity. Nevertheless, adopters were very clear that using aquaculture wastewater to irrigate their vegetable crops had favoured **increase in yields**, representing a promising outcome for their future production activity. Moreover, the value of **fish sales** increased for adopters, driven mostly by catfish: this is an outcome of better aquaculture practices favoured by the training and the need to make the integrated system viable as a whole. Therefore, we can be confident that the FoodLAND project has built the basis for long-term economic **impact** in rural areas of Uganda, which will later drive sustainable food value chains and diverse, more nutritious local diets.

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5. Recommendations for innovation dissemination

The FoodLAND RCTs focused on very specific yet different innovations, implemented in very different local contexts. Therefore, **external validity** is necessarily limited, and researchers and policy practitioners must refrain from drawing too general conclusions in terms of strategies for the promotion of agricultural technology. For instance, the type of **information** provided as part of the treatments focused respectively on climate change and healthiness, could have been conveyed in alternative ways. Differently from the *online* surveys often conducted in the Global North, where the use of a single sentence, or a short paragraph allows to control for confounding effects, in our FoodLAND case studies, the need to develop an entire training session limited the opportunity to control for external factors as well as for the framing and enumerator effects. Equally, the **rates** chosen for the monetary **incentives** (50 EUR flat-rate payment in Morocco; 10% discount in Tanzania; 15% upfront or 5% upfront payment plus 25% payment-by-results in Uganda), though extensively discussed with local partners, might be considered arbitrary, and deviations from these values may potentially lead to different results. Nevertheless, the RCTs allowed to observe significant, recurring **decision-making patterns** that can inform the design of nudges and incentivisation schemes, should local stakeholders (farmer associations, NGOs) or public authorities decide to proceed with large-scale dissemination of the FoodLAND or similar innovations in these same regions. Here, we recap these patterns to derive **policy recommendations**.

First of all, **stated preferences** derived from survey questionnaires that do not generate real consequences for the welfare of the respondents are unreliable, thus making inference, or designing policy interventions based exclusively on this type of information is risky. The most visible demonstration is the ranking of the treatment groups in terms of stated interest against actual installation in Uganda: while group T2 showed the highest levels of interest, they adopted the least. While the detection of revealed preferences is more costly in the short-term (as shown by the expenses for incentives primarily in Uganda), this information could generate much larger benefits in the longer-term, thanks to the improved cost-effectiveness of the resulting incentivisation schemes.

Second, the trials confirmed that innovation adoption is a **complex** and **non-linear** process, which cannot be reduced to a binary variable registered at a given point in time. The **nudges** or financial incentives provided at a certain point of the process, do not necessarily have a persisting impact in later phases. But at the same time, they can reinforce the relationship of **trust** between farmers and the organisations promoting the innovation, improve the **credibility** of the latter, and reinforce the farmer's **commitment** towards the final goal: improving the farm production process and possibly generating associated public goods. In turn, the above dynamics might trigger a process of **self-suggestion** leading the farmer to believe in the usefulness and effectiveness of the innovations despite having limited information to objectively assess these aspects. For instance, several participants declared that they had experienced an increase in their **yields**, or a reduction in **input** requirements which we could not detect while analysing quantitative information about the farming process. Equally, we saw that in Morocco, *ceteris paribus* the farmers who had the opportunity to receive a monetary payment were more likely to discuss the innovation with other peers, and this **word-of-mouth** can possibly result in further enquiries or even uptake. Such considerations suggest that providing small incentives can have indirect beneficial effects beyond uptake and use of the innovation by the farmers directly involved, and beyond the trial.

While the **adoption process** differed significantly between countries, in Figure 72 below we tried to summarise the key **steps** (not present in everywhere) in a systematic way. Our protocol allowed us to “measure” adoption at different stages, thus determining the share of farmers who were “advancing” to the following stages: **(a) intention** was recorded in Morocco and Uganda, not Tanzania, where the beans had to be purchased immediately; **(b) planning** was particularly relevant for Uganda, where a business plan was required, not elsewhere; **(c) purchase** of the innovation took place in Tanzania and Uganda but not in Morocco, where the phone app was installed for free; **(d)**

setting up the innovation was particularly challenging in Uganda, more traditional elsewhere; **(e) trying** (using) entails both the production and (except Morocco) consumption side; **(f) adjustment** was not directly included in our protocol, and refers to the longer-term consequences of the trials. Besides intention, we registered planning and setting up in Uganda, and trying (actual use of the innovations) in all countries. Unfortunately, with the exception of T3 in Uganda, our resources and time were not sufficient for a direct monitoring on-farm, and the assessment of use is only based on the farmers' declarations in the final survey. For future research as well as in the case of large-scale implementation, we warmly recommend that "adoption" is **monitored** along the whole process from intention to on-farm trialling. Where direct audits are unfeasible for logistical or financial reasons (e.g., when the innovation concerns many smallholders scattered around a large territory like in Uganda), random selection of a **subset of farmers** may be an option. Another option could be the identification of **proxies** of adoption or of adequate use which are likely to be associated to achieving the required outcome and that can be easily monitored remotely or without the need for complex measurements. This was done in Morocco, where in the absence of water metres, ENAM conditioned the individual payment to a (collective) threshold in terms of *individual use* of the app that was likely to result in proper water management at farm level. Our analysis revealed that this approach was successful in promoting uptake (installation) and, at later stages, engagement with the app as well as positive spillovers such as discussing the innovation with peers. These achievements entailed limited costs, as the flat-rate payment was capped at 50 EUR, still salient enough.

Figure 72: Overview of the process of innovation adoption

In terms of **strategies** for the dissemination of innovations, our findings confirm that the provision of **information** is less effective than financial incentives. Additionally, when the information does not concern farmers in their capacity of *producers* but focuses, for instance, on the *consumption* side, like in the case of the health benefits of the new bean varieties in Tanzania, its impact does not necessarily transfer to other realms. Indeed, very few farming households consumed the beans despite knowing about their healthiness and the shorter cooking time and this lower need for fuel. Nevertheless, when related to a local situation that farmers are experiencing, like the local impacts of climate change in Morocco, and associated to a financial incentivisation scheme, the provision of detailed information can enhance the impact of the latter.

For what concern small monetary **payments** (including price **discounts**, which is equivalent), we feel that these should *not* be used for innovations that require large investments, like the integrated fish-vegetable farming system in Uganda. On the one hand, they could **backfire** by crowding out farmers' intrinsic motivations or pre-existing intentions, or raising expectations for larger payments in the future. On the other hand, they are subject to moral hazard, as suggested by the relatively large number of fish farmers in Uganda who received the upfront payment (either 15% or 5%) and then did not install the system, or abandoned the project shortly afterwards. Given that the number of adopters was detected through the final survey, and only verified among the T3 groups (where about half of those who had received the upfront payment had abandoned the project even if they knew that they were subject to an audit for receiving the payment-by-result), the real figure could possibly be even lower, and many of these may not be managing the system properly. In turn, we *advise* to use small, time-limited **discounts** to promote the uptake of more "traditional" innovations whose cost is limited, such in the case of the new bean varieties in Tanzania. Although the scale of implementation in this country was limited, and no significant difference was detected between the group who received information and the one who received the discount, in the longer-term we observe more commitment from the farmers in the latter group: they did grow the bean more often than their counterparts. Additionally, while we detected no improvement in farm performance and household wellbeing thanks to the new bean varieties, the RCT allowed introduction of the varieties in the villages, and through further multiplication and word-of-mouth, this niche will likely expand.

Finally, the more complex incentivisation schemes (**payment-by-result** and **collective threshold**) did not seem to represent obstacles to adoption despite the entailed risk of not receiving the sum expected. In both cases, the rate of adoption and further indicators show better performance than with the other strategies (information only in Morocco, upfront payment in Uganda). Therefore, we retain that such incentivisation strategies should be considered more often for promoting agricultural innovation, especially when the latter is likely to generate **public goods** (ecological benefits) or outcomes that are delayed in time, and thus likely to be ignored by farmers when making their adoption decisions. We have already mentioned the advantage of the collective threshold, especially when linked not to the actual objective but to a proxy that can be monitored more easily. We have also raised the issue of **cost** (including the transaction costs of conducting the audits) when it comes to proper payments-by-result. For such reasons, this strategy is only viable if the number of potential adopters is not too large (like in the case of fish farmers as opposed to crop farmers), and the long-term benefits that the innovation could generate are highly valuable and measurable. Compared to the incentivisation scheme adopted in Uganda, we advise to *remove*, or *reduce*, the upfront payment, which should only remain as a way to signal the commitment of the organisation, and possibly trigger "sunk cost fallacy" among the adopters. Second, the cost of monitoring could be reduced by only auditing a *subset* of farmers, randomly selected. The challenge of measuring the results correctly remains, and addressing it is out of the scope of this report.

To conclude, it is important to mention some **limitations** of our study, besides external validity. A first one is that we could not implement a proper cost-effectiveness analysis: on the one hand, the scale of implementation is too small, and the timeframe too short for the innovations to reveal their full potential; on the other hand, the innovations were either provided for free (i.e., the phone app in Morocco), which could not be the case in real market conditions, or no market price was available yet (i.e., the case of the new bean varieties). A second one is the difficulty in implementing a **complex protocol** in the framework of a four-year project, involving many international partners: although all the FoodLAND partners involved in the task were highly committed and did their best, the scope for addressing emerging issues, such as the slow multiplication of the bean seeds, or unfavourable climatic conditions, was limited. Nevertheless, we believe that this task has already generated significant **impact** in the three Food Hubs involved, and it would be interesting to keep observing the developments there, to draw more solid conclusions about the long-term benefits of agricultural development projects and European Union funding.

Appendix: Plan for the impact assessment

This Appendix reports the **workplan** for the **analysis of impact**. More precisely, it contains lists of variables identified for assessing impact based on the pre-registered protocols, and how they must be reworked as part of the **difference-in-differences** approach. It also lists the variables used for the **propensity score matching** analysis.

Outliers: We remove all the values of the outcome variables that are <Q1-3IQR or >Q3+3IQR.

Example of table for the presentation of the results

Variable	Mean baseline (st. dev.)	Mean final (st. dev.)	Diff. final-baseline for non-adopt.	Diff. final-baseline for adopters	Diff. in diff.	Statistic	p-value

Morocco

The variables 1 to 6 need to be analysed separately for “potatoes”, “carrots”, and “onions”. If some variables are missing for specific farmers (because they did not grow the crop), the variables will be assumed to be 0.

1. *Land size:* $m_base_crop_prod_land_sz$ (replace with $m_base_crop_prod_land_sz_last$ if missing) – $m_fina_crop_prod_land_sz$
2. *Production:* $m_base_crop_prod_q_prod$ – $m_fina_crop_prod_q_prod$
3. *Yield:* $m_base_crop_prod_q_prod / m_base_crop_prod_land_sz$ (replace with $m_base_crop_prod_land_sz_last$ if missing) – $m_fina_crop_prod_q_prod / m_fina_crop_prod_land_sz$
4. *Value of production:* $m_base_crop_prod_q_prod * m_base_crop_prod_price_sold$ – $m_fina_crop_prod_q_prod * m_fina_crop_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that crop if missing)
5. *Quantity sold:* $m_base_crop_prod_q_sold$ – $m_fina_crop_prod_q_sold$
6. *Value of sales:* $m_base_crop_prod_q_sold * m_base_crop_prod_price_sold$ – $m_fina_crop_prod_q_sold * m_fina_crop_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that crop if missing)
7. *Cost of inputs:* sum for each unique_id of $m_base_crop_input_cost$ – sum for each unique_id of $m_fina_crop_input_cost$
8. *Energy, water, and weed killer cost:* $m_base_crop_input_cost$ – $m_fina_crop_input_cost$ only for $m_base_crop_input_type ==$ “energy,” “water,” “weed” (separately)
9. *Energy, water, and weed killer quantity:* $m_base_crop_input_cost$ – $m_fina_crop_input_cost$ only for $m_base_crop_input_type ==$ “energy,” “water,” “weed” (separately)
10. *Farm profit:* for the crop specified in $m_base_crop_inpu_crop$ only: $(m_base_crop_prod_q_prod * m_base_crop_prod_price_sold)$ minus sum for each unique_id of: $m_base_crop_inpu_cost$; for the crop specified in $m_fina_crop_inpu_crop$ only: $(m_fina_crop_prod_q_prod * m_fina_crop_prod_price_sold)$ minus sum for each unique_id of $m_fina_crop_inpu_cost$
11. *Farm expenses self-declared:* $m_base_surv_expense_farm$ – $m_fina_surv_expense_farm$
12. *Energy expenses self-declared:* $m_base_surv_expense_energy$ – $m_fina_surv_expense_energy$
13. *Farm sales self-declared:* $m_base_surv_earn_farm_sell$ – $m_fina_surv_earn_farm_sell$
14. *Soil fertilisation practices:* count of practices in $m_base_surv_soil_fertility$ (exclude 0) – count of practices in $m_fina_surv_soil_fertility$ (exclude 0)
15. *Change in specific practices:* $m_base_surv_soil_fertility = 1$ (dummy) – $m_fina_surv_soil_fertility = 1$ (dummy), repeat for values from 1 to 5

16. *Change in late blight (one year)*: $m_base_crop_prod_blight_1year - m_fina_surv_blight_1year$
17. *Change in late blight (five years)*: $m_base_crop_prod_blight_5years - m_fina_surv_blight_5years$
18. *Ranking of water sources*: For each variable in $m_base/fina_surv_irrig_source_*$ replace missing values with 0 and invert the scale so that 5 is the most important ($6 - x$), then make the difference between $m_base_surv_irrig_source_* - m_fina_surv_irrig_source_*$, where $*$ = canal, comtan, spring, well (do not use other typologies of sources)
19. *Water rights hours*: $m_base_surv_wat_right_hrs - m_fina_surv_wat_right_hrs$ (before making the difference, convert to yearly using $m_base/fina_surv_wat_right_hrs_unit$, multiplying by 365/7 if “weekly”, 12 if “monthly”, 365 if daily, 365/4 if “4 days”)
20. *Perceived yield change*: $m_base_crop_prod_chang_yield - m_fina_crop_prod_chang_yield$

The following variables appear only in the final survey, so we cannot use difference-in-differences, and we need to simply test the difference between adopters and non-adopters.

21. *Self-assessed change in late blight*: $m_fina_surv_chang_blight \neq 2.5$, remove 99
22. *Self-assessed impact of the app on blight*: $m_fina_surv_chang_blight_app > 2$, remove 99 and 0
23. *Self-assessed change in yield*: $m_fina_crop_prod_chang_yield > 3$, replace 0 with 3 or remove it
24. *Self-assessed app impact on inputs*: $m_fina_crop_inpu_chang_app > 3$, remove 0, 9 and 99
25. *Self-assessed app impact on irrigation*: $m_fina_surv_chang_irrig_app > 1$, remove 0
26. *Self-assessed change in water rights*: $m_fina_surv_chang_wat_right == 4 \mid 5 > 0$
27. *Self-assessed app impact on yields*: $m_fina_crop_prod_chang_yield_app > 3$, remove 0, 9 and 99

Tanzania

If the variables are missing for specific farmers (because they did not grow the crop), the variables needs to be assumed to be 0.

1. *Land size*: sum for each unique_id of: $t_base_crop_prod_land_sz - t_fina_crop_prod_land_sz$
2. *Land size by variety*: repeat the above for each $t_base/fina_crop_prod_land_sz$ except “other,” unless “other” shows a significant number of farmers producing the same type
3. *Production*: sum for each unique_id of: $t_base_crop_prod_q_prod - t_fina_crop_prod_q_prod$
4. *Value of production*: sum for each unique_id of: $t_base_crop_prod_q_prod * t_base_crop_prod_price_sold - t_fina_crop_prod_q_prod * t_fina_crop_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that variety if missing)
5. *Quantity sold*: sum for each unique_id of: $t_base_crop_prod_q_sold - t_fina_crop_prod_q_sold$
6. *Value of sales*: sum for each unique_id of: $t_base_crop_prod_q_sold * t_base_crop_prod_price_sold - t_fina_crop_prod_q_sold * t_fina_crop_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that variety if missing)
7. *Quantity self-consumed*: sum for each unique_id of: $t_base_crop_prod_q_self - t_fina_crop_prod_q_self$
8. *Cost of inputs*: sum for each unique_id of $t_base_crop_input_cost -$ sum for each unique_id of $t_fina_crop_input_cost$
9. *Single inputs cost*: $t_base_crop_input_cost - t_fina_crop_input_cost$ for each $t_base_crop_input_type$ (separately)
10. *Single inputs quantity*: $t_base_crop_input_q_used - t_fina_crop_input_q_used$ for each $t_base_crop_input_type$ (separately)
11. *Farm profit*: for each unique_id, sum ($t_base_crop_prod_q_prod * t_base_crop_prod_price_sold$) minus sum of $t_base_crop_inpu_cost$; for each unique_id, sum ($t_fina_crop_prod_q_prod * t_fina_crop_prod_price_sold$) minus sum of $t_fina_crop_inpu_cost$
12. *Farm expenses self-declared*: $t_base_surv_expense_farm - t_fina_surv_expense_farm$
13. *Farm sales self-declared*: $t_base_surv_earn_farm_sell - t_fina_surv_earn_farm_sell$
14. *Frequency of consuming beans*: $t_base_surv_beans_cons_freq - t_fina_surv_beans_cons_freq$

15. *Count of nutrition-related diseases experienced*: sum for each unique_id of $t_base_surv_health_* == 1$ (the diseases are *_anem*, *_scur*, *_blind*, *_const*, *_goit*, *_diab*, *_hyper*, *_ulcer*, *_oth*: also count “other”)
16. *Occurrence of specific diseases*: for each disease, $t_base_surv_health_* == 1$, $t_fina_surv_health_* == 1$
17. *Self-assessed health conditions*: $t_base_surv_health_assess - t_fina_surv_health_assess$

The following variables appear only in the final survey, so we cannot use difference-in-differences, and we need to simply test the difference between adopters and non-adopters.

18. *Self-assessed change in variable yield*: $t_fina_surv_chang_yield_vari > 3$, remove 0 and 99
19. *Self-assessed change in health*: $t_fina_surv_chang_health_vari > 3$, remove 0 or replace with 3
20. *Self-assessed change in fuel consumption*: $t_fina_surv_chang_fuel_q > 3$, remove 99
21. *Change in yield by variety*: $t_fina_crop_prod_chang_yield > 3$ after collapsing the sheet to ensure that we have a single observation for $t_fina_crop_prod_type_comb == \text{“standard”}$; test “newline1” vs “standard” and “newline2” vs “standard”)
22. *Self-assessed change in input use*: $t_fina_crop_inpu_chang_vari > 3$, remove 0 and 99, test by each value of $t_fina_crop_inpu_type$
23. *Count of selling channel by variety*: collapse the sheet to ensure that we have a single observation for $t_fina_crop_prod_type_comb == \text{“standard”}$, then count of $t_fina_crop_prod_sell_* == 1$ for the 9 channels, including “other”, test “newline1” vs “standard” & “newline2” vs “standard”
24. *Share of farmers using each selling channel*: collapse the sheet to ensure that we have a single observation for $t_fina_crop_prod_type_comb == \text{“standard”}$ and consider only the farmers for which $t_fina_crop_prod_q_sold > 0$, then % for each selling channel out of sellers, and test difference “newline1” vs “standard” & “newline2” vs “standard”

For the new varieties, we do not have baseline observations, therefore we will compare with the standard varieties, using the final survey observations. For each of the above variables, we will compare $t_fina_crop_prod_type_comb = \text{“newline1”}$ vs “standard” and “newline2” vs “standard”:

25. *Yield*: $t_fina_crop_prod_q_prod / t_fina_crop_prod_land_sz$
26. *Seed rate*: $t_fina_crop_prod_seed_q / t_fina_crop_prod_land_sz$
27. *Maturation days*: $t_fina_crop_prod_mat_days$
28. *Selling price*: $t_fina_crop_prod_price_sold$
29. *Crop losses*: $t_fina_crop_prod_q_loss / t_fina_crop_prod_q_prod$

Uganda

If the variables are missing for specific farmers (because they did not grow the crop), the variables needs to be assumed to be 0.

The following variables must be calculated for all the crops /fish jointly.

1. *Land size (crops)*: sum for each unique_id of: $u_base_crop_prod_land_sz - u_fina_crop_prod_land_sz$
2. *Value of crop production*: sum for each unique_id of: $u_base_crop_prod_q_prod * u_base_crop_prod_price_sold - u_fina_crop_prod_q_prod * u_fina_crop_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that vegetable if missing)
3. *Value of crop sales*: sum for each unique_id of: $u_base_crop_prod_q_sold * u_base_crop_prod_price_sold - u_fina_crop_prod_q_sold * u_fina_crop_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that vegetable if missing)
4. *Value of fish production*: sum for each unique_id of: $u_base_fish_prod_q_prod * u_base_fish_prod_price_sold - u_fina_fish_prod_q_prod * u_fina_fish_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that species if missing)

5. *Value of fish sales*: sum for each unique_id of: $u_base_fish_prod_q_sold * u_base_fish_prod_price_sold - u_fina_fish_prod_q_sold * u_fina_fish_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that species if missing)

The following variables must be calculated for all crop and species, i.e., $u_base_fish_prod_type ==$ "tilapia," "catfish," and for $u_base_fish_prod_type ==$ all those where the numbers are big enough

6. *Land size (crops)*: $u_base_crop_prod_land_sz - u_fina_crop_prod_land_sz$
7. *Crop production*: $u_base_crop_prod_q_prod - u_fina_crop_prod_q_prod$
8. *Value of crop production*: $u_base_crop_prod_q_prod * u_base_crop_prod_price_sold - u_fina_crop_prod_q_prod * u_fina_crop_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that variety if missing)
9. *Crop quantity sold*: $u_base_crop_prod_q_sold - u_fina_crop_prod_q_sold$
10. *Value of crop sales*: $u_base_crop_prod_q_sold * u_base_crop_prod_price_sold - u_fina_crop_prod_q_sold * u_fina_crop_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that variety if missing)
11. *Crop yield*: $u_base_crop_prod_q_prod / u_base_fish_prod_land_sz - u_fina_crop_prod_q_prod / u_fina_fish_prod_land_sz$
12. *Fish production*: $u_base_fish_prod_q_prod - u_fina_fish_prod_q_prod$
13. *Value of fish production*: $u_base_fish_prod_q_prod * u_base_fish_prod_price_sold - u_fina_fish_prod_q_prod * u_fina_fish_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that species if missing)
14. *Fish quantity sold*: $u_base_fish_prod_q_sold - u_fina_fish_prod_q_sold$
15. *Value of fish sales*: $u_base_fish_prod_q_sold * u_base_fish_prod_price_sold - u_fina_fish_prod_q_sold * u_fina_fish_prod_price_sold$ (remove 0s in the prices and replace with the median for that species if missing)
16. *Fish yield*: $u_base_fish_prod_q_prod / u_base_fish_prod_pond_sz - u_fina_fish_prod_q_prod / u_fina_fish_prod_pond_sz$
17. *Cost of crop inputs*: sum for each unique_id of $u_base_crop_input_cost -$ sum for each unique_id of $u_fina_crop_input_cost$
18. *Cost of specific crop inputs*: $u_base_crop_input_cost - u_fina_crop_input_cost$ for $u_base/fina_crop_input_type ==$ "chemfert," "weedk," "organic" (separately)
19. *Quantity of specific crop inputs*: $u_base_crop_input_q_used - u_fina_crop_input_q_used$ for $u_base/fina_crop_input_type ==$ "chemfert," "weedk," "organic" (separately)
20. *Cost of fish inputs*: sum for each unique_id of $u_base_fish_input_cost -$ sum for each unique_id of $u_fina_fish_input_cost$
21. *Cost of specific fish inputs*: $u_base_fish_input_cost - u_fina_fish_input_cost$ for $u_base/fina_fish_input_type ==$ "chemfert," "weedk," "organic" (separately)
22. *Quantity of specific fish inputs*: $u_base_fish_input_q_used - u_fina_fish_input_q_used$ for $u_base/fina_fish_input_type ==$ "water," "energy," "feed" (separately)
23. *Crop farm profit*: for each unique_id, sum ($u_base_crop_prod_q_prod * u_base_crop_prod_price_sold$) minus sum of $u_base_crop_input_cost$; for each unique_id, sum ($u_fina_crop_prod_q_prod * u_fina_crop_prod_price_sold$) minus sum of $u_fina_crop_input_cost$
24. *Fish farm profit*: for each unique_id, sum ($u_base_fish_prod_q_prod * u_base_fish_prod_price_sold$) minus sum of $u_base_fish_input_cost$; for each unique_id, sum ($u_fina_fish_prod_q_prod * u_fina_fish_prod_price_sold$) minus sum of $u_fina_fish_input_cost$
25. *Total profit*: sum the crop (23) and fish (24) profits for baseline and final surveys separately and check the difference in differences
26. *Crop expenses self-declared*: $u_base_surv_expense_farm - u_fina_surv_expense_farm$
27. *Crop sales self-declared*: $u_base_surv_earn_farm_sell - u_fina_surv_earn_farm_sell$
28. *Fish expenses self-declared*: $u_base_surv_expense_fish - u_fina_surv_expense_fish$
29. *Fish sales self-declared*: $u_base_surv_earn_fish_sell - u_fina_surv_earn_fish_sell$
30. *Food expenses*: $u_base_surv_expense_food - u_fina_surv_expense_food$

31. *Receiving farm loans*: $u_base_surv_loan - u_fina_surv_loan$
32. *Receiving farm credit*: $u_base_surv_credit - u_fina_surv_credit$
33. *Capacity of satisfying food needs*: $u_base_surv_food_need - u_fina_surv_food_need$
34. *Number of crops grown*: count: $u_base_surv_crops_grown - u_fina_surv_crops_grown$ (exclude 0 which means “none of the above”)
35. *Number of crops irrigated*: count: $u_base_surv_crops_irrigate - u_fina_surv_crops_irrigate$ (exclude 0 which means “none of the above”)
36. *Number of crops fertilised*: count: $u_base_surv_crops_fert - u_fina_surv_crops_fert$ (exclude 0 which means “none of the above”)
37. *Number of crops consumed*: count of $u_base_surv_cons_freq_* > 0 - u_fina_surv_cons_freq_* > 0$ (out of 16 crops)
38. *Change in consumption frequency of first group of crops*: average of $u_base_surv_cons_freq_* > 0 - u_fina_surv_cons_freq_* > 0$ (out of 16 crops)
39. *Change in consumption frequency of second group of crops*: count of $u_base_surv_cons_crops$ (exclude 0) – count of $u_fina_surv_change_cons_* \neq 99$ (the format of the variable is not the same, although the crops are: in the baseline, it is a list of integer separated by commas, in the final survey we must count the crops where the response is not “I do not consumer this crop”)
40. *Ranking of irrigation water sources*: For each variable in $u_base/fina_surv_irrig_source_*$ replace missing values with 0 and invert the scale so that 3 is the most important ($4 - x$), then make the difference between $m_base_surv_irrig_source_* - m_fina_surv_irrig_source_*$, where $*$ = river, lake, rain, canal, mains, well, pond (“pond” is only available in the final survey, so we just check if it differs between adopters and non-adopters)
41. *Ranking of water discharge places*: For each variable in $u_base/fina_surv_discharge_*$ replace missing values with 0 and invert the scale so that 3 is the most important ($4 - x$), then make the difference between $m_base_discharge_source_* - m_fina_surv_discharge_*$, where $*$ = river, lake, rain, canal, well, land (do not use other typologies of sources)
42. *Frequency of water discharge*: $u_base_surv_discharge_often - u_fina_survey_discharge_often$
The following variables appear only in the final survey, so we cannot use difference-in-differences, and we need to simply test the difference between adopters and non-adopters.
43. *Self-assessed change in yield*: $u_fina_surv_chang_yield_system > 3$, remove 99
44. *Self-assessed change in input use*: $u_fina_surv_chang_system > 3$, remove 99
45. *Change in consumption of specific crops*: $u_fina_surv_chang_cons_* > 3$, remove 99 (where $*$ is the name of each single crop)
46. *Change in use of specific inputs*: $u_fina_crop_inpu_chang > 3$, remove 99, test by each value of $u_fina_crop_inpu_type$, apart from “other”

